

CRITICAL SYSTem Engineering AcceLeration

Platform Builder Prototype – V2

Platform Builder Manual

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CONTENT

1	INTRODUCTION.....	10
1.1	PLATFORM BUILDER BRICK	11
1.2	ROLE OF DELIVERABLE	11
1.3	CRYSTAL PROJECT.....	11
1.4	RELATIONSHIP TO OTHER CRYSTAL DOCUMENTS.....	11
1.5	STRUCTURE OF THIS DOCUMENT.....	11
2	PLATFORM BUILDER MANUAL.....	12
2.1	INTRODUCTION.....	12
2.1.1	<i>Users type</i>	12
2.1.2	<i>Basic concepts</i>	12
2.1.3	<i>Main Goal of the Platform Builder</i>	12
2.1.4	<i>Platform Builder Workflow</i>	12
2.1.5	<i>From Processes to the SEE</i>	13
2.1.6	<i>Platform Builder Meta-model</i>	14
2.1.7	<i>Basics about the Platform Builder Tool</i>	15
2.2	PLATFORM BUILDER REQUIREMENTS	15
2.3	TAILORING PHASE	16
2.3.1	<i>Basic Goal</i>	16
2.3.2	<i>Requirements</i>	16
2.3.3	<i>Tailoring a Process</i>	26
2.4	CONFIGURATION PHASE.....	56
2.4.1	<i>Basic Goal</i>	56
2.4.2	<i>Requirements</i>	57
2.4.3	<i>SEE Selection</i>	57
2.4.4	<i>Tool-Chain Edition</i>	62
2.4.5	<i>IT infrastructure Edition</i>	74
2.4.6	<i>Data (Artifact) Roles Access Edition</i>	82
2.4.7	<i>Update the Process</i>	83
2.5	VALIDATION PHASE.....	84
2.6	PROPAEDEUTIC FUNCTIONS	85
2.6.1	<i>Platform Builder settings Edition</i>	85
2.6.2	<i>EM – Steps – ETFs mapping Edition</i>	89
2.6.3	<i>ETF Catalogues Edition</i>	90
2.6.4	<i>Tool Catalogues Edition</i>	94
2.6.5	<i>Vendor Catalogues Edition</i>	107
2.6.6	<i>Company IT Infrastructure Edition</i>	109
3	DEVELOPER ENVIRONMENT	115
4	INSTALLATION GUIDE.....	116
5	TERMS, ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS.....	117
6	REFERENCES.....	118
7	ANNEX.....	119
7.1	ANNEX I: CATALOGUES	119
7.1.1	<i>EM Catalogue</i>	119
7.1.2	<i>ETF Catalogue</i>	119
7.1.3	<i>Tool Catalogue</i>	122
7.2	ANNEX II: DESCRIPTORS	123

7.2.1	<i>Tool Descriptor</i>	123
7.2.2	<i>IT Infrastructure Descriptor</i>	126

Content of Figures

Figure 1-1: Platform Builder Inputs and Outputs	10
Figure 2-1: Platform Builder - Overview	12
Figure 2-2: Basic Platform Builder Workflow	13
Figure 2-3: Platform Builder core meta-model.....	14
Figure 2-4: Platform Builder IT infrastructure meta-model	15
Figure 2-5: Crystal Reference Library packages.....	17
Figure 2-6: CORE method plug-in.....	18
Figure 2-7: Practices method plug-in.....	19
Figure 2-8: Platform Builder method plug-in.....	20
Figure 2-9: Platform Builder disciplines - view.....	20
Figure 2-10: Engineering Method Steps.....	21
Figure 2-11: New Method Library.....	21
Figure 2-12: Specify path for new Method Library.....	22
Figure 2-13: Import menu item.....	22
Figure 2-14: Import Method Plug-ins.....	23
Figure 2-15: Path to Crystal Reference Library.....	23
Figure 2-16: Method Plug-ins selection.....	24
Figure 2-17: Crystal Reference Library imported.....	25
Figure 2-18: PB-MCP element pattern	25
Figure 2-19: Tailored Process sample	26
Figure 2-20: New PB-MCP.....	27
Figure 2-21: New PB-MCP dialog.....	28
Figure 2-22: New PB-MCP.....	29
Figure 2-23: PB-MCP disciplines.....	29
Figure 2-24: New Activity task.....	29
Figure 2-25: Activity task edition.....	30
Figure 2-26: New EM task.....	31
Figure 2-27: EM task edition.....	32
Figure 2-28: Auto Assign Disciplines.....	33
Figure 2-29: Select target plug-in to assign disciplines.....	33
Figure 2-30: Activities discipline.....	34
Figure 2-31: Engineering Methods discipline.....	35
Figure 2-32: Copy Activities.....	36
Figure 2-33: Select PB-MCP target.....	36

Version	Date	Page
1.0.0	2015-12-10	5 of 127

Figure 2-34: Source Activities plug-in selection.....	37
Figure 2-35: Copy Engineering Methods.....	37
Figure 2-36: Target PB-MCP selection.	38
Figure 2-37: Source Engineering Methods plug-in selection.....	38
Figure 2-38: Method Configuration.	39
Figure 2-39: Method configuration selection.	40
Figure 2-40: New Process.	41
Figure 2-41: New Process dialog.	42
Figure 2-42: Delivery Process created.	42
Figure 2-43: Copy capability pattern.....	43
Figure 2-44: Capability pattern selection.	44
Figure 2-45: Link Activity.....	45
Figure 2-46: Select Activity task.	46
Figure 2-47: Selected Activity.	47
Figure 2-48: Link Engineering Method.	48
Figure 2-49: Select Engineering Method task.	48
Figure 2-50: Selected Engineering Method.	49
Figure 2-51: Add new Engineering Methods.	49
Figure 2-52: Sub-process.	50
Figure 2-53: New child Activity.....	50
Figure 2-54: New Activity group.....	50
Figure 2-55: New Activity from Method Content.....	51
Figure 2-56: Sample of Activity catalogue.	52
Figure 2-57: New EM container.	53
Figure 2-58: EM container.	53
Figure 2-59: New EM from Method content.....	54
Figure 2-60: sample of EM catalogue.....	55
Figure 2-61: Sample of Tailored Process	56
Figure 2-62: Configuring perspective selection	57
Figure 2-63: New SEE creation	58
Figure 2-64: New SEE wizard	58
Figure 2-65: Providing basic info for a new SEE.....	59
Figure 2-66: Sample of SEE view.....	60
Figure 2-67: New SEE from existing SEE	61
Figure 2-68: Providing basic info for a new SEE	61
Figure 2-69: EM description tab.....	63

Figure 2-70: ETFs selection tab.....	64
Figure 2-71: Add Vertical ETFs dialog	65
Figure 2-72: Cross ETFs selection tab	66
Figure 2-73: Add Cross ETFs dialog	67
Figure 2-74: Tool selection tab.....	68
Figure 2-75: Assign Tool dialog	69
Figure 2-76: Process-Tool artifacts mapping tab.	71
Figure 2-77: Internal EM tool-chain building tab.....	73
Figure 2-78: Internal EM tool-chain building tab (2)	74
Figure 2-79: Direct users tab.	75
Figure 2-80: Add Role.....	76
Figure 2-81: Change Role.	76
Figure 2-82: Indirect users tab.....	77
Figure 2-83: Servers.....	77
Figure 2-84: Tool assignments.....	78
Figure 2-85: Edit Server.....	79
Figure 2-86: PCs.....	80
Figure 2-87: Tool assignments.....	81
Figure 2-88: Edit PC.	82
Figure 2-89: Data.....	83
Figure 2-90: Add Role.....	83
Figure 2-91: Update Process.....	84
Figure 2-92: sample of SEE validation report.....	85
Figure 2-93: Catalogues.....	87
Figure 2-94: Tool search assisted criteria - Tool Vendors tab.....	88
Figure 2-95: Tool search assisted criteria: Tools tab	89
Figure 2-96: EM-Steps-ETFs mapping.....	90
Figure 2-97: ETF Catalogues.....	91
Figure 2-98: Add new ETF.....	92
Figure 2-99: Engineering Domains dialog	92
Figure 2-100: Engineering Domain edition	93
Figure 2-101: Tool Artifacts dialog	93
Figure 2-102: Tool Artifact edition	94
Figure 2-103: Tool Catalogues.....	95
Figure 2-104: Vendor selection.....	96
Figure 2-105: Licenses	97

Figure 2-106: Add new license.	98
Figure 2-107: Vertical ETFs.....	99
Figure 2-108: Add Vertical ETFs.....	100
Figure 2-109: Add Cross ETFs	101
Figure 2-110: Tool Extensions	102
Figure 2-111: Add Extended By Tools.....	103
Figure 2-112: Tool IT Requirements.	104
Figure 2-113: System Requirements menu.	104
Figure 2-114: Add System Requirements dialog.	105
Figure 2-115: Network Requirements memu.....	106
Figure 2-116: Minimum Bandwidth.	106
Figure 2-117: Resident and Remote Software menu.	107
Figure 2-118: Add Service dialog.....	107
Figure 2-119: Vendor Catalogues.....	108
Figure 2-120: Edit Vendor.....	109
Figure 2-121: Machines.....	110
Figure 2-122: Field edition.....	110
Figure 2-123: Type selection.....	111
Figure 2-124: Services.....	111
Figure 2-125: Network machines.....	112
Figure 2-126: Network services.....	113
Figure 2-127: Network connections.....	114
Figure 7-1: ETF definition example in the ETF catalogue.....	122
Figure 7-2: ETF example pair.....	122
Figure 7-3: Example of Tool descriptor.....	125

Content of Tables

Table 5-1: Terms, Abbreviations and Definitions.....	117
Table 7-1: EM fields' information.....	119
Table 7-2: ETF information in the ETF catalogue	120
Table 7-3: Artifacts information in the ETF catalogue	121
Table 7-4: ETF pairs of the kind consumer-provider	121
Table 7-5: Tool descriptor information.....	124
Table 7-6: IT requirement element for tools.....	124
Table 7-7: Artifacts element for tools	125
Table 7-8: Machines.....	126

Version	Date	Page
1.0.0	2015-12-10	8 of 127

Table 7-9: Services	126
Table 7-10: Networks	127

1 Introduction

The Platform Builder approach, which is involved in the CRYSTAL project with Grant Agreement No. ARTEMIS-2012-1-332830 and detailed in the specification document [D602-021, 2014], is implemented by the Platform Builder Prototype. The identified Platform Builder approach is based on definition of ontologies, described through data catalogues that are used in two different defined phases: tailoring phase and configuring phase. The tailoring phase addresses features to describe a specific development process using process activities (activity catalogue) and applying Engineering Methods (EM Catalogue). The tailoring phase output i.e. the tailored process is the main input of the Configuring phase, which addresses features to configure the System Engineering Environment (SEE) using Tool and Engineering Tool Function Catalogues. The Platform Builder Modeler (PB-Modeler) implements the tailoring and configuring phases on top of Eclipse framework and it supports two windows perspective: *Authoring* and *Configuring*. The Authoring perspective includes all interface views, which are relevant to the Tailoring phase features while the Configuring perspective includes Configuration phase related features.

Note: In the Eclipse Platform, a Perspective determines the visible actions and views within a window.

Figure 1-1: Platform Builder Inputs and Outputs

Basically, in the Tailoring phase, the authoring perspective of the EPF Composer is used to edit and modify a tailored Process with the support of activities catalogue and the EM catalogue, which were defined in CRYSTAL project.

Eclipse plugins implemented on top of EPF Composer support the Configuring perspective which facilitates, using the Tool catalogue and the ETF catalogue, the SEE configuration. The SEE configuration encompasses Tool-Chain and IT infrastructure where Tools shall be deployed.

The PB-Modeler produces a first SEE configuration model that later on is validated in order to have a consistent and coherent final SEE configuration model which shall be suitable for a Tool-Chain deployment.

1.1 Platform Builder Brick

This brick named Platform Builder is a brick intended to allow different companies to define their development processes for embedded critical systems based on the Reference Technology Platform (RTP) and configure the System Engineering Environment (SEE) selecting the more suitable tools according to different criteria, especially IOS capabilities (The IOS consists of a specification for achieving common Tool & Data Interoperability in heterogeneous Systems Engineering development environments), for supporting such processes. Once configured, this brick allows validating the obtained SEE.

The Platform Builder prototype objective is to support and facilitate the definition of development platforms, which shall perform an identified and detailed development process. This implementation is based on a method that facilitates the SEE configuration and Tools selection. In order to facilitate the configuration of a SEE and the selection of the Tools, a common meta-model to describe a Tool in a unique way is defined which ends up providing a standardized Tool descriptor. Tool Providers using the Tool Descriptor meta-model are then able to define their Tools providing a common interface to the identify Tools. This facilitates the Tools selection in order to accomplish appropriate tool-chain and also facilitates the Tool-chain deployment.

1.2 Role of deliverable

This document describes the Platform Builder User Story in terms of operative functions to be performed by an end user who has to describe and configure a System Engineering Environment. References to real tools have been removed, but on the OSLC page you can see the list of tools that support OSLC.

1.3 CRYSTAL project

CRYSTAL as an ARTEMIS Innovation Pilot Project (AIPP) takes up research results of previous projects in the field of Reference Technology Platform (RTP) and Interoperability Specification (IOS) (e.g. CESAR, MBAT ...) and enhances and matures them with the clear aim of industrialisation take-up.

RTP and IOS will allow loosely coupled tools to share and interlink their data based on standardized and open Web technologies that enable common interoperability among various life cycle domains. This reduces the complexity of the entire integration process significantly. Compared CRYSTAL is strongly industry-oriented and will provide ready-to-use integrated tool chains having a mature technology-readiness-level (up to TRL 7).

Following the ARTEMIS mission to strengthen the European market for Embedded Systems, CRYSTAL fosters cross-domain reusability (Aerospace, Automotive, Health and Rail) and pursuits driving forward the Interoperability Specification towards standardisation.

1.4 Relationship to other CRYSTAL Documents

The Platform Builder Manual is a document that provides information about how to use the Platform Builder Prototype V1 deliverable. Then this document details how the Platform Builder Specification V1 [D602.021, 2014] has been implemented. Furthermore, present Meta-models on this deliverable are further described on the document Meta-model specification – V2 [D602.012, 2015].

1.5 Structure of this document

This document is structured as the following: section 1 introduces the Platform Builder; section 2 is the Platform Builder manual with figures to illustrate features and functionalities of the implemented prototype; section 3 shows the procedures and tools for developing the Platform Builder; section 4 describes the steps to install and configure the Platform Builder; in section 5 a summary of terms, abbreviations and definitions is shown; section 6 are the references to other documents; finally the section 7 contains some annexes, description of catalogues, the tool and IT infrastructure descriptors.

Version	Date	Page
1.0.0	2015-12-10	11 of 127

2 Platform Builder Manual

2.1 Introduction

This document details the user story of how to use the Platform Builder. Before starting using it, please read this section for gaining some basic knowledge about the main purpose and main components of the Platform Builder.

2.1.1 Users type

Different users shall use the PB prototype and each user has different roles such as:

- **Process Architect** is skilled to describe a Tailored process and it will use the Authoring Perspective in the PB prototype;
- **SEE Architect** is skilled to configure a development environment and it will use mainly the Configuring Perspective of PB prototype;
- **IT Engineer** is skilled to manage ETF (Engineering Tool Functions are the set of engineering functions that a Tool is able to provide) Tool Catalogue, Tool Catalogue, Company Tool Catalogue and IT infrastructure.

2.1.2 Basic concepts

There are two basic concepts that are the main focus of the Platform Builder. Their definitions are:

- **Product Development Process** is a process envisaged for developing a product or a part of the product development.
- **System Engineering Environment (SEE)** is a framework where a Tool-chain will be instantiated within the organization IT infrastructure to perform a process (Product Development Process) relevant to a project scope. This framework will be set up with the project data.

2.1.3 Main Goal of the Platform Builder

The main goal of the Platform Builder is to allow a System Architect to derive from a Product Development Process (Figure 2-1) the needed (and validated) System Engineering Environment for executing it.

Figure 2-1: Platform Builder - Overview

2.1.4 Platform Builder Workflow

Figure 2-2 shows the overall Platform Builder Workflow and highlights, in orange, the phases of the workflow that are in the scope of the CRYSTAL project.

Version	Date	Page
1.0.0	2015-12-10	12 of 127

Figure 2-2: Basic Platform Builder Workflow

Platform Builder performs these three phases:

1. **Process Tailoring.** Tailor – define– a Product Development Process with its activities applying Engineering Methods: Tailored Process;
2. **SEE Configuration.** Configure –derive– from the Tailored Process the required System Engineering Environment (SEE) for instantiating this Tailored Process: Configured SEE;
3. **SEE Validation.** Validate – check– the Configured SEE in order to see if it can be instantiated as it is defined in the company: Validated SEE.

At the end of this process the SEE Architect has a Validated SEE that can be instantiated (manually in this version of the Platform Builder) in the company and performs the Tailored Process taking as much as advantage as possible of interoperability specification (IOS) in order to improve the overall process.

2.1.5 From Processes to the SEE

From a technical point of view, the Platform Builder makes use of two different catalogues for enabling the mapping between the engineering methods which are needed in the activities of the Product Development Process and the engineering tool functions provided by tools. Furthermore, Process Activities have to be defined and formalized based on ontology. Within the CRYSTAL project, two catalogues are formalized for providing the needed information:

- Catalogue of Engineering Methods (EM). Used in the tailoring phase of the Platform Builder for defining which Engineering Methods are applied in each activity of the Product Development Product. This catalogue is built by a Process Engineer in Industrial companies.
- Catalogue of Engineering Tool Functions (ETF). This catalogue has two types of Engineering Tool Functions: internal ETF and IOS services. This catalogue is used within two different scopes:
 - Used in the Configuration phase for mapping EMs of the Tailored Process to ETF(s) (one EM can be mapped to more than one ETF, meaning that the EM makes use of those ETF(s)),
 - Used for defining Tools. This is done by using a Tool Editor that will allow the creation of Tool Descriptors (one Tool Descriptor per Tool) and allows identifying the set of ETF that are provided by this tool. Those Tool Descriptors are later used for creating:
 - The RTP Tool Catalogue: the set of Tool Descriptors of the tools that belong to the RTP (Tools supporting completely or partially IOS)
 - The Available Tool Catalogue: the set of Tool Available Descriptor of the tools, which are available in the company.

The usage of the information provided by the ETF catalogue (for describing Tools and mapping EM to ETFs) supports later the Platform Builder configurator to perform an automatic mapping between the tools that can be used in each engineering method of the Product Development Process.

The following section shows the basic workflow of the Platform Builder and the envisaged Meta-model.

Version	Date	Page
1.0.0	2015-12-10	13 of 127

2.1.6 Platform Builder Meta-model

Before starting the User Story, it is necessary to obtain some basic knowledge about the main concepts used in the Platform Builder. For doing so, in this section it is presented the set of meta-models, which are useful to understand the already quoted PB concepts. The complete meta-model is decomposed as follows:

- Core Meta-model;
- IT Meta-model.

2.1.6.1 Core Meta-model

The Core meta-model contains the high-level elements used in the Tailoring and Configuration phases. For a deeper view on the MM elements as well as on the MM itself, please consult the deliverable Meta-model specification – V2 [D602.012,].

Figure 2-3: Platform Builder core meta-model

2.1.6.2 IT Meta-model

The IT infrastructure Meta-model (as required for the project) defines the IT infrastructure to where the tool-chain will be deployed. This IT infrastructure is the platform that provides the basis for the data structure, roles, applications and functionality being delivered to the end users in order to allow them to perform activities using the plugged-in “tool-chain”. Figure 2-4 presents the IT Meta-model. For a deeper view on the IT MM elements as well as on the IT MM itself, please consult the deliverable Meta-model specification – V2 [D602.012,].

Figure 2-4: Platform Builder IT infrastructure meta-model

2.1.7 Basics about the Platform Builder Tool

For PB prototype we have mainly two different perspectives: Authoring and Configuring. The Authoring perspective includes all interface views relevant to the Tailoring phase features, while the Configuring perspective includes Configuration phase features and in addition validation and reporting features.

Tailoring phase is the Authoring perspective of EPF composer, including the PB-MPC method that is proper to the PB approach.

Configuring perspective is a new perspective of EPF Composer and it includes all PB implemented plugins.

EPF Composer is based on Unified Model Architecture (UMA) and SPEM 1.1 [SPEM, 2005]. Herein, when document refers to elements already defined in the meta-model SPEM1.1 and UMA, it will use the term **EPF elements**. While elements are part of the new implementation of PB approach, it will use the term **PB elements**.

2.2 Platform Builder Requirements

The requirements for being able to use the Platform Builder are to have:

- The EPF-Composer installed on your computer;
- Access to the Platform Builder plugins. Those plugins provide some utilities for the Tailoring phase, the editors that allow configuring the SEE taking as input the Tailored Process and validation functionalities;
- Access to the Platform Builder Reference Library, which provides samples of Activity and EM catalogues (the end users are in charge to populate Activities and EM catalogues for each domain); and guidance about Platform Builder usage;
- Access to the Platform builder method content plug-in -PB-MCP-. Method content plugin for EPF-Composer that provides elements to be used in the Tailoring phase (part of the Platform Builder Reference Library);

- Access to the RTP Tool Catalogue;

2.3 Tailoring phase

2.3.1 Basic Goal

In this phase the Process Engineer defines the Product Development Process. For doing so, it must specify:

- Activities of the process;
- Engineering Methods applied in each activity.

In order to support this phase the Platform Builder makes use of the features provided by the EPF Composer. Next section explains how EPF Composer can be used for tailoring a process in such a way that later it can configure the associated SEE.

One of the results obtained in this phase is the list of Engineering Methods (List of EMs). In the Configuration phase it will be derived from this list the Tools to be used i.e. the Tool Chain.

2.3.2 Requirements

The needed requirements for tailoring a process in the Platform Builder are the following:

- EPF Composer
- Platform Builder Reference Library
- PB Methodology

This section basically explains these elements.

Once all the requirements are fulfilled it is possible to go on with the tailoring phase steps. It can be summarized as authoring the process by using the functionality of EPF Composer but then the Process Engineer has to use the methodology for assigning EMs to Activities.

2.3.2.1 Tailoring with EPF Composer

This approach consists in using EPF-Composer as it is for the Tailoring phase of the Platform Builder, because it does provide most of the required features. However, as one of the main goals of the Tailoring phase is to obtain a List of EMs, some part of the tailoring is based and guided through two basic elements:

- **Platform Builder Reference Library:** that provides several information elements to be used during the tailoring of a process highlighting the Activity and EM catalogues.
- **PB Methodology:** methodology explaining how to use the PB-MCP elements in a proper way when tailoring a process in order to obtain the List of EMs.

In the following sections, those elements are explained.

2.3.2.2 Platform Builder Reference Library

As it has been said, the Platform Builder Reference Library provides elements to be used when tailoring the process. In this way, the Platform Builder Reference Library provides to the Process Engineer the following information to be used when tailoring the process:

- **Activity Tasks:** A generic set of activities to be used as high-level activities in the Product Development Process. These objects are created as EPF Task elements (in Activity Catalogue) and are categorized in the Activity Discipline.

- EM Tasks: A catalogue of Engineering Methods (EMs) to be used in the activities of the Product Development Process. Those objects are created as EPF Task elements and are categorized in the EM Discipline.
- A generic set of artifacts to be used in the EM.

Figure 2-5: Crystal Reference Library packages.

The Platform Builder Reference Library is defined using the EPF Composer tool and it is based on **method contents** packaging, to structure the information it provides. The Activities and EMs are provided as tasks in the respective method content packages. The list of packages provided by the Platform Builder Reference Library are:

- **CORE** contains re-usable activities. All tasks added to this package are interpreted as Activities that can be re-used when defining a new PB-MCP method content. If needed new method content plugins can be created to structure activities of other domain, even of the own company. See CORE.Aerospace.base_aerospace in Figure 2-6.

Figure 2-6: CORE method plug-in.

- **Practices** contains re-usable EMs. All tasks added to this package are interpreted as EMs that can be re-used when defining a new PB-MCP method content and then be included in a tailored process. Like in the CORE method plug-in if needed can be created new method plugins to structure the EMs of other domains. See Practices.Aerospace.base_aerospace in Figure 2-7

Figure 2-7: Practices method plug-in.

- **Guidances** contain explanation for the PB Methodology and PB modeler tool. This package is used to describe guidelines relevant to PB method and PB Modeler tool, using EPF Composer itself. This helps to navigate the provided guidances as part of the Platform Builder reference Library.
- **Process** contains life cycle processes that can serve as guideline to compose the tailored process. Process package shall be used to describe the system life cycle process as applied in each domain for a system to be developed. This process can be considered a guideline for defining a tailored process and discovering activities to be defined. Actually, no domain processes are defined in this package. It is up to end users to populate it. Processes are used in every domain.
- **PlatformBuilder** contains instances of PB-MCP method content to be used for the process tailoring. Under Platform Builder package, instances of PB-MCP (Figure 2-8) shall be created for each selected use case.

Figure 2-8: Platform Builder method plug-in.

Activities and EMs defined in CORE and Practices are re-usable tasks for defining new PB-MCP. When tailoring a process as part of a created PB-MCP, new tasks to define Activities and EMs can be defined. They will not be re-usable, being defined for the current PB-MCP only.

Thus, the core elements of the Crystal Reference Library are the two types of EPF Tasks (Activity Tasks and EM Tasks) categorized by Disciplines to represent the Activities and EM when tailoring the process.

Figure 2-9: Platform Builder disciplines - view

The PB Methodology explains how to use those types of Tasks when tailoring the process in order to assign EM (Engineering Methods) to Activities. This is done through disciplines. The Activity Discipline and EM Discipline are grouped inside the Platform Builder Discipline.

An Engineering Method is composed of detailed steps, during EM definition; it is possible to define steps with basic features of EPF Composer (Figure 2-10). Steps will be used to map IOS capabilities (or detailed ETFs)

Figure 2-10: Engineering Method Steps.

2.3.2.2.1 Platform Builder Reference Library Installation

The precondition for using this system for tailoring the process is to install the Platform Reference Library in the EPF-Composer. For doing so, you should perform the following steps (each step includes a figure showing the process):

1. Download the **Platform Builder Reference Library**
2. Create a new Method library
 - a. **File->New->Method Library** (Figure 2-11)

Figure 2-11: New Method Library.

- b. Specify **Path** for Method Library ->**Finish** (Figure 2-12)

Figure 2-12: Specify path for new Method Library.

- 3. Import to the EPF composer the Crystal Reference Library, downloaded in the step 1
 - a. **File->Import...** (Figure 2-13)

Figure 2-13: Import menu item.

- b. Select **Method Plug-ins** (Figure 2-14)

Figure 2-14: Import Method Plug-ins.

- c. Specify directory where the **Platform Builder Reference Library** has been placed (Figure 2-15) after decompress the [material for PB assessment](#).

Figure 2-15: Path to Crystal Reference Library.

- d. **Select all** method plug-ins (Figure 2-16)

Figure 2-16: Method Plug-ins selection.

The Platform Builder Reference Library imported is shown in the Figure 2-17.

Figure 2-17: Crystal Reference Library imported.

2.3.2.3 PB Methodology

This methodology explains how to use the elements of the PB-MCP when tailoring a process. This methodology is especially focused in guaranteeing the proper usage of Activity Tasks (Activity Discipline elements) and EM Tasks (EM Discipline elements) during the tailoring of the process for obtaining a valid List of EMs.

Figure 2-18: PB-MCP element pattern

A tailored process consists of a list of activities and each activity of a list of engineering methods. To allow the Platform Builder can read correctly a process this must be composed as a list of PB-MCP element patterns ().

A PB-MCP element pattern represents an activity with its engineering methods and is structured as:

Version	Date	Page
1.0.0	2015-12-10	25 of 127

- Activity group, is an EPF activity (Activity-1 in Figure 2-18 **A**)
- Activity which contains the information of the process activity, name, description, roles, etc., is an EPF task(Activity-1 in Figure 2-18 **B**)
- EM group, is an EPF activity (EM in Figure 2-18 **C**) and contains the list of Engineering Methods of the Activity (In Figure 2-18 there is only one EM, but can be more)
- Engineering Methods, contains the information related to EMs, name, description, artifacts, etc... And are EPF tasks (EM-1 in Figure 2-18 **D**)

It is important to highlight that when a Process Engineer builds the process in the Process View, when mapping a Task to such activity (either Activity Task or EM Task) he can modify the default provided values of Roles, Artifacts in order to adopt the ones already defined in the company.

Figure 2-19 shows a sample of how it is the obtained result. Elements identified as **1** are EPF Activity elements that are mapped to Activity Tasks (from the Activity Discipline) which are identified as **2**. Whereas elements of type **3** are EPF Activities mapped to EM Tasks (from the EM Discipline) that are identified as **4**.

Presentation Name	Index	Predecessor
Process	0	
1 Define Requirements	1	
2 Define Requirements	2	
3 EM	3	
4 Add a new Requirement with its properties	4	
4 Modify requirement	5	
4 Delete requirement	6	
1 Manage requirements during the process	7	
2 Manage requirements during the process	8	
3 EM	9	
1 Navigate/view requirements list	13	
2 Navigate/view requirements list	14	
3 EM	15	

Figure 2-19: Tailored Process sample

2.3.3 Tailoring a Process

Once the Platform Builder Reference Library is installed in the EPF-Composer we can make use of all the elements, including the EM catalogue.

Then in the Process View, when creating an element of the type Process, the System Architect has to follow the PB Methodology. To summarize the steps:

- Create an Activity Element for each activity that there is in the process and map them to Tasks which are defined in the Activity Discipline. For sure, the System Architect can make use of other Task elements (defined in its company Method Content Plug-in).
- Create an Activity Element embedded in an activity element mapped to an Activity Task for each EM to be used in this. This last created activity must be mapped to an EM Task of the EM Discipline (EM catalogue). In this case, it is clearly recommended to make use of the tasks which are defined inside the EM Discipline of the PB-MCP.

The following subsections show the way for tailoring a process. For doing so, they will be used some new utilities developed to help users in this tailoring phase. Once all the Activities have been created and properly mapped to Activity Tasks and EM Tasks, we will have obtained the List of EM for using in the Configuration phase. But, before explaining the process of assigning activities to a process, and EMs to activities in the

tailoring phase, first should be detailed how to prepare the needed infrastructure and import the needed information: Activity and EM catalogues.

2.3.3.1 Creation of a PB-MCP

Under Platform Builder package a new instance of PB-MCP shall be created:

1. Platform Builder -> New PB-MCP

Figure 2-20: New PB-MCP.

2. Write the name of the new PB-MCP in the text box, to identify it as a PB-MCP the name must finish with "**PB-MCP**", this is mandatory and is added automatically. Tip: in order to have the new PB-MCP under the Platform Builder package, it is necessary to write package names separated with dot: i.e.: PlatformBuilder.TP_instances.Ucxxx_

Figure 2-21: New PB-MCP dialog.

3. After the creation of the PB-MCP it can be observed in the library tree. See Figure 2-22

Figure 2-22: New PB-MCP.

The newly created PB-MCP will have two catalogues:

- **Activity Catalogue**
- **EM Catalogue**

Tasks under those catalogues are categorized with disciplines as needed by the PB methodology.

Figure 2-23: PB-MCP disciplines.

2.3.3.2 Adding Activities and EMs under their catalogues

When the user has the need to populate Activity and EM catalogues manually he has to create a new Task in the respective catalogue.

To add a new Activity:

1. Select **Tasks** under **Activity Catalogue**. Right click the mouse and select **New → Task**.

Figure 2-24: New Activity task.

- Write down the name of the new task that in this case will represent an Activity.

Figure 2-25: Activity task edition.

To add a new EM:

- Select **Tasks** under EM Catalogue. Right click the mouse and select **New → Task**.

Figure 2-26: New EM task.

2. Write down the name of the new task that in this case will represent an EM.

Figure 2-27: EM task edition.

2.3.3.3 Assigning Disciplines

The PB method works using Disciplines (EPF element). This EPF element permits to use defined Activities and EMs during tailoring phase. Auto Assign Disciplines creates and assigns to Disciplines all defined Activities and EMs within the created PB-MCP. This function is mandatory to have a PB-MCP usable for the tailoring phase, and should be used after define all Activities and EMs to make these available in the process tailoring.

To assign automatically disciplines in a PB-MCP:

1. Select **Platform Builder** → **Auto Assign Disciplines** (Figure 2-28)

Figure 2-28: Auto Assign Disciplines.

- 2. Select the **target plug-in** where the disciplines will be created (Figure 2-29)

Figure 2-29: Select target plug-in to assign disciplines.

All the tasks from the Activity and EM catalogues are now classified with their disciplines. (Figure 2-30 and Figure 2-31)

Figure 2-30: Activities discipline.

Figure 2-31: Engineering Methods discipline.

2.3.3.4 Re-use Activities and Engineering Methods

To re-use the Activity tasks and the Engineering Method task from the Platform Builder Reference Library there are two functionalities in the Platform Builder menu that copy the items in the corresponding catalogue of PB-MCP and then assign their correct disciplines:

- Copy Activities
- Copy Engineering Methods

2.3.3.4.1 Copy Activities

Copy Activities permits to copy all activities defined in the CORE package.

1. Select **Platform Builder** → **Copy Activities** (Figure 2-32)

Figure 2-32. Copy Activities.

2. Select the **PB-MCP target** (Figure 2-33)

Figure 2-33: Select PB-MCP target.

3. Select the **source** plugin with Activities (Figure 2-34)

Figure 2-34: Source Activities plug-in selection.

2.3.3.4.2 Copy Engineering Methods

Copy EMs permits to copy all Engineering Methods defined in the Practices package.

1. Select **Platform Builder** → **Copy Engineering Methods** (Figure 2-35)

Figure 2-35: Copy Engineering Methods.

2. Select the **target** plug-in (Figure 2-36)

Figure 2-36: Target PB-MCP selection.

3. Select the Engineering Methods **source** plugin (Figure 2-37)

Figure 2-37: Source Engineering Methods plug-in selection.

2.3.3.5 Method Configuration

For using the Activities and the Engineering Methods copied or created in the PB-MCP that will be used for tailoring the process first is necessary to define a configuration.

1. Optionally the user can create a new Configuration or select an existing one.
2. Double click on the **Configuration** chosen to open it (Figure 2-38).

Figure 2-38: Method Configuration.

3. Select only the created PB-MCP for current UC (i.e. Ucxxx-PB-MCP Figure 2-39) and save configuration.

Figure 2-39: Method configuration selection.

2.3.3.6 The Process

To create a new Process:

1. Select **Delivery Process** under **Processes**.
2. Right click on mouse and select **New Delivery Process**.

Figure 2-40: New Process.

3. Specify the **Name** of new Tailored Process in the dialog box opened. (Figure 2-41 **A**)

Figure 2-41: New Process dialog.

- 4. Select the configuration. (Figure 2-41 B)
- 5. Once created the process select the **Work Breakdown Structure** tab.

Figure 2-42: Delivery Process created.

To populate the process, two different recursive workflows are possible:

1. Apply capability pattern
2. Add sub-process

Both workflows create the **PB-MCP element pattern** to be populated using Activities and EMs. Case 1 is semi-automatic, while case 2 is manual.

2.3.3.6.1 Apply capability pattern

To apply capability pattern:

1. Right mouse button on the process item
2. Select **Apply Pattern** and select **Copy** (Figure 2-43)

Figure 2-43: Copy capability pattern.

3. Select **Capability Pattern** → **Activity-1** (Figure 2-44). A new Activity with an Engineering Method is copied in the process.

Figure 2-44: Capability pattern selection.

4. Select Activity from catalogue

Presentation Name	Index	Predecessors	Model Info	Type	Planned	Repeat...	Multipl...	Ongoing	Event...	Optional
TP-UCxxx	0			Delivery Pro...	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Activity-1	1			Activity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Activity-1 A	2			Task Descri...	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
EM	3			Activity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				
EM-1	4			Task Descri...	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Properties **B**

Task Descriptor : Activity-1

General Information

Provide general information about this task descriptor.

Name: Restore

Presentation name: Restore

Optional
 Multiple Occurrences
 Planned
 Suppressed
 Event Driven
 Ongoing
 Repeatable

Index	Presentation Name	Dependency

Add
Edit
Remove

Method task: **C** Link Method Element...

Figure 2-45: Link Activity.

- a. Select the **Activity-1** task (Figure 2-45 **A**)
- b. Open **Properties View, General** tab (Figure 2-45 **B**)
- c. Click on **Link Method Element** button (Figure 2-45 **C**)
- d. Select an Activity from Activity Catalogue (Figure 2-46)

Figure 2-46: Select Activity task.

- e. The Activity is then linked (Figure 2-47)

The screenshot shows a software interface with a table of tasks and a detailed view of a selected task descriptor.

Presentation Name	Index	Predecessors	Model Info	Type	Planned	Repeat...	Multipl...	Ongoing	Event-...
TP-UCxxx	0			Delivery Pro...	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Activity-1	1			Activity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
define conceptual model	2			Task Descri...	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
EM	3			Activity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
EM-1	4			Task Descri...	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

The 'Task Descriptor : Activity-1' panel is open, showing the 'General Information' section. The 'Name' field is set to 'define conceptual model' and the 'Presentation name' field is also set to 'define conceptual model'. There are 'Restore' buttons for both fields.

Figure 2-47: Selected Activity.

5. Select Engineering Method from catalogue

The screenshot shows the software interface with the 'Task Descriptor : EM-1' panel open. The table above shows the 'EM-1' task selected.

Presentation Name	Index	Predecessors	Model Info	Type	Planned	Repeat...	Multipl...	Ongoing	Event-...
TP-UCxxx	0			Delivery Pro...	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Activity-1	1			Activity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
define conceptual model	2			Task Descri...	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
EM	3			Activity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
EM-1	4			Task Descri...	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

The 'Task Descriptor : EM-1' panel shows the 'General Information' section. The 'Name' field is 'EM-1' and the 'Presentation name' is 'EM-1'. There are 'Restore' buttons for both. Below these are checkboxes for 'Optional', 'Event Driven', 'Multiple Occurrences', 'Ongoing', 'Planned', 'Repeatable', and 'Suppressed'. A dependency table is present with columns for 'Index', 'Presentation Name', and 'Dependency'. To the right of the table are 'Add', 'Edit', and 'Remove' buttons. At the bottom, the 'Method task' is set to '<< NONE >>' and there is a 'Link Method Element...' button.

Figure 2-48: Link Engineering Method.

- a. Select **EM-1** task (Figure 2-48 **A**)
- b. Open **Properties** View, **General** tab (Figure 2-48 **B**)
- c. Click on **Link Method Element** button (Figure 2-48 **C**)
- d. Select an Engineering Method from Engineering Method catalogue (Figure 2-49)

Figure 2-49: Select Engineering Method task.

- e. The Engineering Method is then linked (Figure 2-50)

Figure 2-50: Selected Engineering Method.

6. Add additional Engineering Methods

Figure 2-51: Add new Engineering Methods.

- Select **EM** activity and click with the right mouse button
- Select the **New Child** → **Task Descriptor** menu item.
- Change the name in the **Properties** view.

2.3.3.6.2 Add sub-process

Using EPF composer functionalities, the Process can be populated from scratch. It is possible create a sub-process conform to the PB-MCP element pattern.

- Activity group (Figure 2-52 **A**)
- Activity (Figure 2-52 **B**)
- EM container (Figure 2-52 **C**)
- EM (Figure 2-52 **D**)

Figure 2-52: Sub-process.

1. To create a new Activity group:
 - a. Select **New Child** → **Activity** (Figure 2-53)

Figure 2-53: New child Activity.

- b. Write down the name of the Activity group (Figure 2-54)

Presentation Name	Index	Predecessors	Model Info	Type	PI
TP-UCxxx	0			Delivery Pro...	
Activity-1	1			Activity	
define conceptual mo	2			Task Descri...	
EM	3			Activity	
Fault-tree generati	4			Task Descri...	
my-new-Activity	5			Activity	

Figure 2-54: New Activity group.

2. Add new Activity

- a. Under new Activity group (i.e. my-new-Activity) add a new activity using Add from Method Content... (Figure 2-55)

Figure 2-55: New Activity from Method Content.

- b. Select a Task from Activity catalogue (Figure 2-56)

Figure 2-56: Sample of Activity catalogue.

3. Create EM container
 - a. Under the new *Activity group* (i.e. my-new-Activity) create a **New Child → Activity** (this is the new EM container) (Figure 2-57)

Figure 2-57: New EM container.

- b. Specify EM in the new created Activity. (Figure 2-58)

Figure 2-58: EM container.

4. Add a new EM
 - a. Under new EM container add a new EM selecting **Add from Method Content...** (Figure 2-59)

Figure 2-59: New EM from Method content.

- b. Select a Task from EM catalogue (Figure 2-60)

Figure 2-60: sample of EM catalogue.

2.3.3.7 Tailored Process Result

Once this process has been finished, a Tailored Process that also provides a List of EM has been obtained. (Figure 2-61)

Presentation Name	Index	Predecessor
Process	0	
Define Requirements	1	
Define Requirements	2	
EM	3	
Add a new Requirement with its properties	4	
Modify requirement	5	
Delete requirement	6	
Manage requirements during the process	7	
Manage requirements during the process	8	
EM	9	
Link requirement with its architectural models	10	
Link requirement with its implementation models	11	
Link requirement with its test cases and test reports	12	
Navigate/view requirements list	13	
Navigate/view requirements list	14	
EM	15	
View requirements filtered by different grouping's views	16	
View requirements filtered by different stakeholder's perspectives	17	
View requirements filtered by different viewpoints	18	

Figure 2-61: Sample of Tailored Process

2.4 Configuration phase

2.4.1 Basic Goal

The basic goal of the configuration phase in the Platform Builder is to configure the SEE taking, as a starting point, the Tailored Process obtained in the Tailoring Phase. In order to do so, the System Architect in this phase has to:

- Map each EM defined in the Tailored Process to ETF (as many as required);
- For each ETF assigned in step 1, select the Tool that is able to provide it in the process (the tool is to be selected from the Domain Tool Catalogue);
- Specify the IOS links that are necessary inside each EM.
- Define the basic IT infrastructure requirements of the process;
- Specify roles access to tool artifacts.
- Generate the whole IT infrastructure requirements of the SEE, combining the IT infrastructure requirements coming from the process (defined in step 3), and those coming from the selected tools in step 2.

Once this process is finished, the System Architect has defined the Tool-Chain that will be used in the Product Development Process and the IT infrastructure needs.

Before starting to configure the SEE in this phase, check the next section in order to know about the requirements. Once you have checked these requirements, you can move to the sections detailing each step of the configuration phase.

2.4.2 Requirements

Before starting the configuration phase, the following requirements must be satisfied:

- A complete Tailored Process with a List of EM;
- EPF Composer properly installed with the Platform Builder plugins ;
- Access to the Domain Tool Catalogue (for the Engineering Function Mapper). This is the complete set of Tool Descriptors of Tools included in such catalogue and is to be obtained from the RTP;
- A catalogue of Tool Vendors;
- A catalogue of ETFs.

When all these requirements are fulfilled, you can go on with the configuration phase steps:

- Tailored process selection;
- Engineering tool function mapping;
- IT infrastructure process definition;

2.4.3 SEE Selection

The first step to be done is selecting the SEE to be configured. For doing so, the System Architect should open the EPF-Composer where the Configuration phase plugins have been installed. Then, he should change to the **Configuring** perspective.

Figure 2-62: Configuring perspective selection

Once the **Configuring** perspective is opened, the System Architect can select the SEE to be configured from the explorer window at the left side of the screen.

It can happen that the SEE to configure has not yet been created. If this is the case, check the section 2.4.3.1 for further guidance on it.

2.4.3.1 SEE Creation

In the case the SEE object to be configured has not yet been created, the System Architect has to create a new SEE object and link it to the tailored process for which the System Architect wants to generate the SEE.

Figure 2-63: New SEE creation

By selecting the menu item "New SEE" the wizard "Create a new SEE" will be displayed. There are two ways to create a new SEE:

- Create empty SEE
- Copy from existing SEE

Figure 2-64: New SEE wizard

2.4.3.1.1 Create empty SEE

In this case, it creates a new SEE from a Tailored Process.

Figure 2-65: Providing basic info for a new SEE

In the second page:

- Fill the **Name** text box with the name of the SEE (Figure 2-65 **A**)
- Select the process that the SEE will be created (Figure 2-65 **B**)
- Fill the **Description** text box with the description of the SEE (Figure 2-65 **C**)

Once the Tailored Process is selected, the system extracts the required information, especially the List of EM, in order to start the Configuration Process itself. The system supports the creation of several SEE objects associated to the same tailored process, as a possibility for exploring different ways of configuring the SEE for the same process.

Once the SEE process is imported, it is shown at the left side of the window together with the main sections of the SEE to be configured: data artifacts and IT Process Infrastructure (see next picture).

Then the System Architect can either perform the:

- Tool-Chain edition;
- IT infrastructure process definition;
- Process data definition.

These steps are further explained in the following sections.

Figure 2-66: Sample of SEE view

2.4.3.1.2 Copy from existing SEE

In this case, it creates a new SEE from an existing SEE

Figure 2-67: New SEE from existing SEE

Select an existing SEE in the table (Figure 2-67).

Figure 2-68: Providing basic info for a new SEE

In the second page:

- Fill the **Name** text box with the name of the SEE (Figure 2-68 **A**)
- Fill the **Description** text box with the description of the SEE (Figure 2-68 **B**)

The system makes a copy of the original SEE, assigning the new name and description.

As in the previous section, the SEE is shown at the left side of the window together with the main sections of the SEE to be configured: data artifacts and IT Process Infrastructure.

2.4.4 Tool-Chain Edition

In this step, the System Architect can:

- configure the Engineering Tool Functions (ETF) for each EM in the list;
- select the most suitable tool for providing the selected ETF (both IOS services and internal functions);
- link the selected tools through the IOS services they provide.

In order to do so, the System Architect does the following steps for each EM, which composes the usual workflow:

1. The System Architect selects an EM of the process (grouped per process activity) then the ETF mapper for this EM is shown;
2. Then, the System Architect chooses the ETFs that will be used for performing the EM. In future versions, it is expected that if you use a generic EM, the system will fill in this information. But anyway the System Architect will be always allowed to edit it if needed;
3. Once the ETFs have been selected, the System Architect can choose the Tool that will be used for each ETF. The SEE configurator provides facilities for selecting the most appropriate tools;
4. Later, the System Architect maps the process artifacts “Process Artifacts” defined in the Tailored Process with the tool artifacts “Tool Artifacts” used/provided by the selected Tools (these artifacts are in fact the artifacts used/provided by the Tools in the selected ETFs);
5. Then, the System Architect links the selected tools for this EM through their ETF (IOS services) in order to establish the Tool Chain for this EM.

In order to perform this process, the editor provides the following tabs for each EM:

- **Description:** In this tab (see Figure 2-69), the mapper shows basic information about the EM including the list of already mapped ETFs to this EM and the selected tools.
- **ETFs:** This tab provides the functionality to be used by the System Architect for selecting the ETFs to be mapped to the EM.
- **Tools:** The selection of the Tool that will provide each ETF is done in this tab.
- **Artifacts:** This tab provides the features for mapping process artifacts to tool artifacts.
- **Toolchain:** The System Architect uses this tab for linking tool artifacts and building the tool chain (this is the internal part of the EM).

In the following sections, the steps and associated tabs in the mapper are detailed.

2.4.4.1 EM Description

This tab is just an information pane about the selected EM in the explorer window at the left of the screen. So, this tab does not provide any editing feature.

The most important information this screen provides are:

1. Selected ETFs for this EM. In orange, it is shown the selected ETFs which are not yet covered by the tools selected for this EM (see next point);
2. Selected Tools for providing the ETF to be used in this EM.

Figure 2-69: EM description tab.

2.4.4.2 ETFs Selection

The System Architect uses this tab for selecting the ETFs that will be utilized for performing the EM. The tab is divided into two main parts, on top the selected ETFs, which are divided into Vertical and Cross, at the bottom all the artifacts of the selected ETFs are shown (Figure 2-70).

Figure 2-70: ETFs selection tab

In the Vertical ETFs tab (Figure 2-70 **A**) the selected Vertical ETFs are shown, here the System Architect can filter the selected ETFs by Engineering Domain selecting it in the drop down menu (Figure 2-70 **C**), also can show only the IOS ETFs checking the IOS check button (Figure 2-70 **D**).

The **Reset Engineering Method** button (Figure 2-70 **G**) permits to clean previous ETFs and tool selection of EM.

To add to ETFs click on the **Add** button (Figure 2-71 **E**), then the **Add Vertical ETFs** dialog will be shown.

Figure 2-71: Add Vertical ETFs dialog

The **Add Vertical ETFs** dialog also shows a table with the ETFs that can be added and the artifacts of the ETFs selected in the table.

The System Architect can filter the available ETFs by Engineering Domain selecting it in the drop down menu (Figure 2-71 **A**), and show only the IOS ETFs checking the **Only IOS** check button (Figure 2-71 **B**), similarly to the way we’ve done in the previous window.

When the System Architect selects an IOS ETF the counterpart IOS ETF is selected automatically.

By clicking the **Add** button (Figure 2-71 **C**) the selected ETFs are added to the EM and the dialog is closed. The recently added ETFs will appear in the **Selected ETFs** table of the Vertical ETFs tab (Figure 2-70 **A**). This list of **Selected ETFs** shows the ETFs mapped to the EM while the list of **Selected ETFs Artifacts** shows the list of Artifacts used/provided by the ETFs listed (Figure 2-70).

The process to remove one of the ETFs is:

1. The System Architect selects the ETFs to be removed. Several ETF's can be selected at the same time;
2. Then the System Architect clicks the **Remove** button. The lists of selected ETFs and **Selected ETFs Artifacts** are updated accordingly.

The **Cross** ETFs tab (Figure 2-72 **B**) works in a very similar way to the **Vertical** ETFs tab, the selected Vertical ETFs are shown, here the System Architect can filter the selected ETFs by Engineering Domain selecting it in the drop down menu (Figure 2-72 **C**),

Figure 2-72: Cross ETFs selection tab

To add to ETFs click on the **Add** button (Figure 2-72 **D**), then the **Add Cross ETFs** dialog will be shown.

Figure 2-73: Add Cross ETFs dialog

The **Add Cross ETFs** dialog also shows a table with the Cross ETFs that can be added and the artifacts of the selected ETFs in the table.

In this case the System Architect must select the **Target Engineering Domain** (Figure 2-73 **A**) which will be applied to the selected Cross ETFs, then the System Architect can filter the available Cross ETFs by Engineering Domain selecting it in the drop down menu (Figure 2-73 **B**), and show only the IOS ETFs checking the **Only IOS** check button (Figure 2-73 **C**).

When the System Architect selects an IOS ETF the counterpart IOS ETF is selected automatically. By clicking the **Add** button (Figure 2-73 **D**) the selected ETFs are added to the EM and the dialog is closed. The recently added ETFs will appear in the **Selected ETFs** table of the Cross ETFs tab (Figure 2-72 **B**). This list of **Selected ETFs** shows the ETFs mapped to the EM while the list of **Selected ETFs Artifacts** shows the list of Artifacts used/provided by the ETFs listed (Figure 2-70).

The process to remove one of the selected Cross ETFs is:

1. The System Architect selects the Cross ETFs to be removed. Several ETF's can be selected at the same time;
2. Then the System Architect clicks the **Remove** button. The lists of selected Cross ETFs and **Selected ETFs Artifacts** are updated accordingly.

2.4.4.3 Tools Selection

This tab (see Figure 2-74) provides features that facilitate the process of selecting the tools to be used in the SEE. Then, the usual way of working in this tab is the following:

Figure 2-74: Tool selection tab.

- The System Architect selects the ETF he wants to support from the ETF list (Figure 2-74 A). This list shows all the selected ETFs in the previous step. ETFs in orange text are not yet satisfied by any selected tool, i.e. no tool assignment for this ETF has been done yet. The table below the ETF list (Figure 2-74 B) shows the selected tools that satisfy the ETF selected in the list. If the ETF is supported by some tools this tool will be listed in the table of selected tools for *selected ETF* (Figure 2-74 B). The system Architect clicks the **Assign Tool to selected ETF** button, then the **Assign Tool** dialog is shown (Figure 2-75).

Figure 2-75: Assign Tool dialog

- In the **Qualified Tools** table (Figure 2-75 D) the tools that support the selected ETF are listed.

3. The list of qualified tools can be filtered by tool name or vendor name writing in the text box (Figure 2-75 **A**).
4. The System Architect can filter the qualified tools list showing only the preferred tools or hiding the tools of the blacklist (Figure 2-75 **B**).
5. In the same way tools can be filtered showing only the tools of preferred vendors or hiding the tools of the blacklist vendors (Figure 2-75 **C**).
6. The System Architect selects the tool to assign, then information about the tool appears in the bottom of the dialog (Figure 2-75 **E**), the name and version, the description (Figure 2-75 **F**) and the list of ETFs supported by the tool (Figure 2-75 **H**).
7. The list of ETFs provided by this tool also provides the following information:
 - a. If an ETF is used in this EM and if it is already covered by other tool: **Covered** label and black colour;
 - b. If an ETF is used in this EM and if it is already covered by this tool: **Covered** label and green colour;
 - c. If an ETF is used in this EM and if it is not yet covered: **Not covered** label and orange colour;
 - d. If an ETF is not used in this EM: **Not assigned** label and red colour.
8. The System Architect selects the ETFs to the EM that will be covered by this tool (Figure 2-75 **H**). Notice that if an ETF which hasn't been added before to the EM is selected, it is automatically added to the EM.
9. Once the process of adding a tool is finished, the selected ETFs move from orange to black in the ETF list (Figure 2-74 **A**) Some important remarks concerning it:
 - a. Several tools can be selected for satisfying the same ETF;
 - b. If a tool is selected for satisfying an ETF but it also provides other ETF that are needed in this EM, these are not implicitly assigned but it should be done explicitly using the editor.
10. Then, the lists of **Selected Tools** (Figure 2-74 **B**) is updated accordingly. This pane shows the selected tools for satisfying the ETF selected in (**A**), for this very EM. The list of selected tools for the EM (Figure 2-74 **E**) is also updated;
11. The list of **Selected Tools** shows the tools that have been selected for satisfying the ETFs which are used in this EM (Figure 2-74 **E**).

When we add a tool that can be extended or extends other tools, the SEE shows **Assign Tool** dialog again with these other tools and asks to the System Architect if he wants to add them. This process is repeated each time we add tools that are extended by or extend other tools.

To remove one of the Tools in (Figure 2-74 **B**) or (Figure 2-74 **E**), the steps to be performed are the following:

1. The System Architect selects in (Figure 2-74 **B**) or (Figure 2-74 **E**) the Tool to be removed. Several Tools can be selected at the same time;
2. Then the System Architect clicks the **Remove** button (Figure 2-74 **D**) or (Figure 2-74 **F**) and the lists are updated accordingly.

2.4.4.4 Mapping Process Artifacts to Tool Artifacts

This process is performed by the System Architect using the **Artifacts** tab (Figure 2-76). This allows the System Architect to communicate which tool artifacts are mapped to each process artifact. This mapping is done as follows:

1. The System Architect selects:
 - a. a process artifact - **Process Artifact** - (only one) in the list of **Process Artifacts** (Figure 2-76 **A**);

Version	Date	Page
1.0.0	2015-12-10	70 of 127

- b. and one or several tool artifacts - **Tool Artifact** - in the list of **Tool Artifacts** (Figure 2-76 **B**).
2. After that, the System Architect clicks the **Add** button (Figure 2-76 **D**);
3. Then, this mapping is included in (Figure 2-76 **C**) (a list of artifact mappings in this EM).

Figure 2-76: Process-Tool artifacts mapping tab.

The list of **Process artifacts** (Figure 2-76 **A**) shows in orange the process artifacts that have not yet been mapped to any tool artifact.

Below are some rules to be known about this **Process artifacts to Tool Artifacts** mapping:

- The same **Tool Artifact** (pair tool – artifact) can be mapped to more than one **Process artifact**.
- A **Process Artifact** can be mapped to more than one **Tool Artifact** (pair tool – artifact).
- The pane of **Tool Artifact** (Figure 2-76 **B**) shows an entry for each pair tool – artifact existing in the EM. In other words, this implies that if the same type of artifact is provided by more than one tool, this pane will show one entry for each tool providing/using it.

To remove one or several artifact mappings in (Figure 2-76 **D**), the process to be performed is the following:

1. The System Architect selects in (Figure 2-76 **C**) the mappings to be removed and;
2. Then the System Architect clicks the **Remove** button (Figure 2-76 **E**).

2.4.4.5 Tool-Chain Building

In parallel to the Artifact mapping, the System Architect can also start to build the Tool Chain. This is done through the linking of the selected tools for this EM and through the ETFs of IOS service type that have been selected.

The Tool Chain building of an EM is done through the tab Toolchain that can be seen in Figure 2-77. In this case, the System Architect links tools in the following way:

1. The System Architect double clicks a pair Tool – ETF (IOS Service) in the Providers list (Figure 2-77 **A**) or in the Consumer list (Figure 2-77 **B**)
2. Then the SEE selects automatically one valid counterpart provider (Figure 2-77 **A**) or consumer (Figure 2-77 **B**) depending in which list has been done the double click in the previous step. Moreover, this list will only show valid counterparts
3. Afterwards, the user can change the pre assigned counterpart if needed, selecting any other of the valid counterparts
4. Next, he can press the **Add** button (Figure 2-77 **F**)
5. Then, the new link is shown in the list (Figure 2-77 **C**)
6. If needed, any link can be deleted by pressing the **Remove** button (Figure 2-77 **G**)

The System Architect can also add automatically the selection of all the valid counterparts by clicking the **Auto** button (Figure 2-77 **D**). In this case, the system makes a proposal of links, but the engineer should review them.

The SEE configurator allows the same pair Tool – ETF that has been selected in the EM to be used in more than one link. Moreover, the pairs Tool-ETF that have not yet been used in any link are marked in orange.

The tab has a text box (Figure 2-77 **E**) where the architect can write **Notes** freely.

Figure 2-77: Internal EM tool-chain building tab.

A graphic representation of the toolchain is shown (Figure 2-78 **A**) at the bottom of the **Toolchain** tab. It is allowed to move the diagram items to improve the visualization of the toolchain. By clicking the **Redraw** button (Figure 2-78 **B**) the system will redraw the toolchain items trying another distribution of the items. This graph will be exported in the report generation, as we will see below.

Figure 2-78: Internal EM tool-chain building tab (2)

2.4.5 IT infrastructure Edition

The IT infrastructure edition serves for defining the IT infrastructure of the process. The definition of the IT infrastructure is optional in a SEE. The main inputs for setting the IT Infrastructure of a SEE are the tools selected in the SEE and its requirements specified in their Tool Descriptors. This information is completed in the editor with information about the number of users per each tool, and how tools are grouped in machines.

Then, the process for defining the IT infrastructure of a SEE once selected the tools is based on two steps:

1. Indicate the number of users for each Tool. Direct for tools and indirect for servers.
2. Defining the machines (and their HW and SW requirements) for servers and PC/Workstations

2.4.5.1 IT Tool Edition

The IT Tool Infrastructure editor is used for establishing the number of users for each tool. It is divided into three main parts:

- On the top general information of the selected tool is shown.
- On the bottom part two tabs are shown:
 - **Direct users**
 - **Indirect users**

Direct users

Version	Date	Page
1.0.0	2015-12-10	74 of 127

The **Direct users** tab (Figure 2-79) is used to specify the number of users that will play a role in this tool. Inside this tab a nested tree structured in: activities, EM, ETF and roles is shown. Roles selected in the tailoring process phase to perform activities are added automatically to every instance of ETF used in this activity.

This structure helps the System Architect to know where is used the tool, and the roles that should have access to the tool according to the information of the tailored process from which this SEE derives.

Figure 2-79: Direct users tab.

Moreover, if needed the System Architect can also add and remove roles. Another role can be added to an ETF by selecting it and clicking the right mouse button, then click on the **Add Role** menu item (Figure 2-80). Notice that only the roles defined in the tailored process can be added.

Figure 2-80: Add Role.

On the right side it is shown the information of the selected item in the tree.

- **Activity**
- Engineering method (**EM**)
- Engineering tool function (**ETF**)
- **Role**. It is possible to change the role by selecting in the drop down list (Figure 2-81).
- Number of **Users** of this role. To select the number of users a spinner button is used (Figure 2-79 **A**).

Figure 2-81: Change Role.

Once the numbers of users for every role is defined, the System Architect may indicate the number of parallel users that can work with this tool (Figure 2-79 **B**).

Indirect users

In the **Indirect users** tab (Figure 2-82) are shown the tools (clients) that have the actual tool as remote software. For every client tool are shown the maximum users and the parallel users. The System Architect can edit the number of **Parallel users** (Figure 2-82 **A**) and the number of **Maximum users** (Figure 2-82 **B**) for the edited tool.

Figure 2-82: Indirect users tab.

2.4.5.2 Servers Edition

The IT Infrastructure Servers editor is used to define the requirements of the server machines needed in the SEE.

When the editor is opened automatically a server machine is created for every tool whose deployment is selected as Server in the tool catalogue, and are not yet assigned to a server machine.

The editor shows a tree-table with the servers and its requirements. The first level of the tree shows all the servers defined in the SEE. For every server a basic set of requirements is shown (Figure 2-83 **A**):

- OS family
- OS version
- RAM(GB)
- HDD(GB)
- Architecture

In the second level of the tree hang for each server its hosted tools (Figure 2-83 **B**). And every tool includes a list of requirements that come from the Tool Catalogue (Tool Descriptor) (Figure 2-83 **C**).

Figure 2-83: Servers.

The definition of server IT Infrastructure involves two main activities.

1. Assign server tools to servers
2. Define server requirements

Three actions can be done to assign tools to servers (Figure 2-84). By right clicking in a tool:

- **Move tool.** The tool can be moved to an existing server or a new one. After that, if the source server doesn't have any tool it will be removed.
- **Copy tool.** Tool can be copied to an existing server or a new one. This is used when the same tool has to be deployed in more than one server.
- **Remove tool.** Remove a tool from a server is possible only if this tool is assigned to another tool too. A tool must be assigned at least to one server.

Figure 2-84: Tool assignments.

Define server requirements can be done in two ways.

- From the tools requirements. By double clicking on the tool requirements, you can select them. Then by right clicking on the server and selecting the item menu **Calculate requirements** the requirements of the server will be adapted to the tools requirements.
- With item menu **Edit Server** of the same contextual menu the server editor window will open (Figure 2-85). Then you can edit all the server requirements:
 - **Server name**
 - **OS family**
 - **OS version**
 - **RAM (GB)**
 - **HDD (GB)**
 - **Architecture**
 - **Processor family**
 - **Processor version**

Figure 2-85: Edit Server.

2.4.5.3 PC's Edition

The IT Infrastructure PCs editor is used to define the requirements of the computers needed in the SEE. The way to use it is very similar to the Servers editor.

When this editor is opened, the PB automatically creates a PC for every tool whose deployment is selected as Workstation in the tool catalogue and that hasn't yet been assigned to a PC. Also it is possible to add, remove PCs selecting the corresponding menu item. See Figure 2-87.

The editor shows a tree-table (Figure 2-86) with the PCs and its requirements. The tree is organized in three different levels: the first level for PCs, the second for Tools deployed in the PC, and the third for the requirements of the tool.

For every PC the basic set of requirements currently shown is:

- **OS family**
- **OS version**
- **RAM(GB)**

- **HDD(GB)**
- **Architecture**

The tools assigned to each PC are shown as said in the second level. And every tool includes the requirements defined in the Tool Catalogue.

The roles that can use the tools assigned to the PC are also shown, along with the number of users for each role that will use this tool in this PC. Usually, for PCs the number of users for each role will be one (assuming personal computer), but when talking about workstations not assigned to a single person the number of users for each role can increase.

PC / Tools	OS family	OS version	RAM (GB)	HDD (GB)	Arch
pc-1 Systems Modeler Adapter Test Generator	Windows	Windows-8	4	1000	X86
pc-2 Systems Modeler	Windows	Windows-8	16	2000	X64
pc-3 Yet Another Quality Manager Tool			0	0	X64

Figure 2-86: PCs.

For defining the PC IT Infrastructure there are two main activities to perform.

1. Assign tools to PCs
2. Define PC requirements

Four actions can be done for assigning tools to PCs (Figure 2-87).

- **Add tool.** A dialog with a list of available tools is shown, then just select the desired tool to be added to this PC.
- **Move tool.** The tool can be moved to an existing PC or a new one.
- **Copy tool.** The tool can be copied to an existing PC or a new one.
- **Remove tool.** This action will remove the selected tool from the PC.

Figure 2-87: Tool assignments.

In the same way that the Servers editor, the definition of the PC requirements can be done by two ways.

- From tools requirements. First select for each tool deployed in the PC the minimum requirements the tool needs. Then by clicking with the mouse right button on the PC and selecting the item menu **Calculate requirements** the requirements of the PC will be adapted to the tools requirements.
- With item menu **Edit PC** of the same contextual menu the server editor window will open (Figure 2-88). Then you can edit all the server requirements:
 - **PC name**
 - **OS family**
 - **OS version**
 - **RAM (GB)**
 - **HDD (GB)**
 - **Architecture**
 - **Processor family**
 - **Processor version**
 - **Number of users per role.** Number of users of each role that will have access to this PC.

Figure 2-88: Edit PC.

2.4.6 Data (Artifact) Roles Access Edition

The **Data editor** (Figure 2-89) is designed as a tree-table that contains all the Tool Artifacts mapped to the selected Process Artifact. The former are shown grouped by Activity and Engineering Methods.

Figure 2-89: Data.

Roles can be assigned to each Tool Artifact by clicking the right mouse button and selecting from the menu item **Add Role** (Figure 2-90).

Figure 2-90: Add Role.

Permissions for each role on this artifact can be edited simply by clicking on the check box. Possible permissions are:

- **Create**
- **Update**
- **Delete**
- **Query/Read**

2.4.7 Update the Process

If the original tailored process has experienced some modifications the System Architect can update the SEE process, for doing so just right click with the mouse in the process item of the main tree (Figure 2-91), on the left side of the window, to open the contextual menu. Then click on the **Update Process** menu item (Figure 2-91 A) to open the **Update Process** dialog, which displays a summary of the changes.

Figure 2-91: Update Process

2.5 Validation phase

The validation can be performed by the Platform Builder->Validate SEE menu and applies to current opened SEE.

The validation performs the following checks:

- ETF coverage: checks that all the selected ETFs are covered by tools which are in the catalogue
- ETF Toolchain connection: checks that all the selected IOS ETFs are connected in the toolchain (typically consumer and producer)
- Tool availability: checks that the tools selected by the ETFs are available in the company. A tool could be present in the catalogue but not available in the company,
- IT Infrastructure: checks the tool IT requirements (Operating System, CPU type, RAM, HDD) against the available IT infrastructure. The architect could have designed a physical architecture but it could not be satisfied by the IT infrastructure available at the company.

At the end of the validation, it is generated a textual report which lists the result of each step described above.

The step titles are shown in bold, the result of each step can be success (in green) or something wrong (in red). In case of lacks or inconsistency, a list of explaining items is detailed just below the related activity name.

Once the report has been generated, it is available a context menu for exporting the result as a text file.

Following an example of the report generated by the validation activity.

Figure 2-92: sample of SEE validation report.

2.6 Propaedeutic functions

In order to configure and validate properly a SEE it is necessary to prepare the Platform Builder specifying and editing the needed catalogues, therefore some editors have been developed. The main purposes are:

- Load the catalogues
- Establish selection criteria of ETFs, tools, etc.
- Populate company catalogues
- Define the IT infrastructure of the company

Next subsections provide information about the different features for preparing the information to be used in the configuration phase.

2.6.1 Platform Builder settings Edition

Platform Builder settings interface has two main utilities:

- Load the catalogues needed for the Platform Builder modeller.
- Establish criteria in order to facilitate tool selection.

The catalogues that can be loaded (Figure 2-93) are:

- **RTP Tool Catalogue.** The Reference Technology Platform (RTP) tool catalogue contains detailed tool descriptions provided from tool vendors.
- **Company Tool Catalogue.** This catalogue contains tools descriptors form tools developed by the company or tools acquired that aren't referenced in the RTP tool catalogue.
- **Available Tool Catalogue.** It contains the list of licenses of tools that the company has acquired and are thus available for use in the company. It refers both to the RTP tool catalogue and the Company tool catalogue.
- **ETF Official Catalogue.** Contains the generic Engineering Tool Functions.
- **ETF Own Catalogue.** The Platform Builder modeler allows the company to define their own Engineering Tool Functions.
- **Generic EM Official Catalogue.** Contains the generic relations between Engineering Methods, Steps and Engineering Tool Functions that are used to map automatically EMs with ETFs.
- **EM Own Catalogue.** The company can define their relations between EMs, Steps and ETFs.
- **IT company/department infrastructure descriptor.** The IT infrastructure of the company collects information about Information Technology. In detail some infrastructure requirements such as:
 - Network definition
 - machines included in the infrastructure
 - supported services
- **RTP Vendor Catalogue.** Contains information about the tool vendors that provide the RTP tool catalogue.
- **Company Vendor Catalogue.** Used to define tool vendors, needed for the Company Tool Catalogue, those are not included in the RTP Vendor Catalogue.

In order to use the Platform Builder modeler should be available at least a tool catalogue (RTP or Company), a vendor catalogue (RTP or Company) and a ETFs catalogue (Official or Own). Usually, the basic combination will be the RTP Tool Catalogue, RTP Vendor Catalogue and ETF Official Catalogue.

Note: any change in the catalogues affect all the already created SEEs and will be applied to all new SEE that will be created.

To update any catalogue you can browse (Figure 2-93 **A**) for the corresponding XML file, or write/paste the path to the file in the edit box, then click on the button **Update** (Figure 2-93 **B**). Then the catalogue is internally copied in the Platform Builder catalogues path and loaded.

Figure 2-93: Catalogues.

The **Tool search assisted criteria** tab (Figure 2-94 and Figure 2-95) is designed to select the preferred Tool Vendors or Tools, or to add them to a black list. Both of them work in the same way:

- To add an item to the preferred list, first select it in the left table (A) (**Tool Vendors** or **Tools**), then click on the > button (D) of the preferred table (B).
- To remove an item from the **Preferred list**, first select it in the **Preferred** table (B) then click on the < button (E).
- To add an item to the **Black List**, first select it in the left table (A) (**Tool Vendors** or **Tools**), then click on the > button (F) of the **Black List** table (C).
- To remove an item from the **Black List**, first select it in the **Black List** table (C) then click on the < button (G).

Note: any change in the tool search assisted criteria affect all the already created SEEs and will be applied to all new SEE that will be created.

Figure 2-94: Tool search assisted criteria - Tool Vendors tab

Figure 2-95: Tool search assisted criteria: Tools tab

2.6.2 EM – Steps – ETFs mapping Edition

EM - Steps - ETFs mapping editor is used to map steps from Engineering Methods to Engineering Tool Functions in order to automate the ETFs selection by the System Architect (Figure 2-96).

This mapping allows the system to assign automatically ETFs to EMs when a SEE is created. A tailored process is compound of Activities, those Activities have EMs and EMs have Steps. When a SEE, linked to a tailored Process, is created, the PB Modeler checks, for each EM (and its steps), if there exists an entry in the EM-Steps-ETFs mapping catalogue. If this is the case the predefined ETFs are assigned to this EM in the SEE. If this not the case, the EM is left empty without ETFs pre-assignment.

To create a new mapping entry in the EM–Steps–ETFs catalogue the System Architect can select a Method Content Plugin in the drop down list Method Plug-in (Figure 2-96 A), then in the left tree the EMs, Steps and ETFs already mapped will be shown (Figure 2-96 B).

In the right table (Figure 2-96 I) a list of Engineering Tool Functions is shown, they can be filtered by:

- **IOS** (Figure 2-96 E). If the IOS check box is selected only the IOS ETFs will appear.
- **Engineering Domain** (Figure 2-96 F). Only the ETFs of the selected Engineering Domain will appear.
- **IOS Operation** (Figure 2-96 G). Only the ETFs with the selected IOS Operation will appear.
- **Search** box (Figure 2-96 H). ETFs can be searched by name.

To map ETFs to a Step just select the Step in the tree (Figure 2-96 B), select the ETFs in the table (Figure 2-96 I) and click on the "Assign" button (Figure 2-96 C).

Remove mappings can be done in three levels, always with the "Release" button (Figure 2-96 **D**):

- Remove an ETF: with an ETF selected, clicking **Release** button
- Remove all mapped ETFs of a step: with a Step selected, clicking **Release** button.
- Remove all mappings of steps for an EM: with an EM selected, clicking **Release** button.

Figure 2-96: EM-Steps-ETFs mapping.

2.6.3 ETF Catalogues Edition

In the ETF Catalogues the System Architect can review the ETFs available in the Platform Builder and add, remove or edit the ETFs of the Company catalogue (Own ETF Catalogue).

On the left side of the editor a tree with all the ETFs is shown (Figure 2-97 **A**). The tree is organized by catalogues, Company catalogue and RTP catalogue, inside the catalogues the ETFs are grouped by engineering domain.

When clicking in an ETF all its information is shown in the right side (Figure 2-97 **B**):

- **Name**
- **ID**
- **Version**
- **Description**
- **Type**
- **IOS Operation**

- **IOS Specification**
- **Engineering Domain**
- **Tool Class**
- **Counterpart**
- **Artifacts**

A description of this fields and their meaning is available at section 7.1.2.

Figure 2-97: ETF Catalogues.

To add a new ETF in the ETF Company catalogue the System Architect can click the mouse right button in the **Company catalogue** item of the tree or in an Engineering Domain item (inside the ETF Company Catalogue), and select the **Add new ETF** menu item. The new ETF will be created and it can be edited in the right panel (Figure 2-98 B).

Note: The RTP Catalogue is not modifiable by the Platform Builder Modeler interfaces, it is only readable.

Figure 2-98: Add new ETF.

The System Architect can add, edit and review Engineering Domains clicking in the **Edit Engineering Domains** button (Figure 2-97 C), then the **Engineering Domains** dialog is shown (Figure 2-99).

Figure 2-99: Engineering Domains dialog

The list of Engineering Domains are divided into **Company Catalogue** (Figure 2-99 **A**) and **RTP Catalogue** (Figure 2-99 **B**). In the **Company Catalogue**, Engineering Domains can be added, edited and removed.(Figure 2-100).

Figure 2-100: Engineering Domain edition

By clicking the **Edit Artifacts** button (Figure 2-97 **D**) the **Tool Artifacts** dialog is shown. In this dialog can be added, edited and revised both the list of Company Catalogue artifacts and the RTP Catalogue artifacts.

Figure 2-101: Tool Artifacts dialog

Like the Engineering Domains, only the Company Catalogue Artifacts can be added, edited or removed (Figure 2-102).

Figure 2-102: Tool Artifact edition

2.6.4 Tool Catalogues Edition

The editor introduced in this section allows System Architect to edit the different tool catalogues used in the PB solution. On the left side there is a tree (Figure 2-103 **A**) allowing the navigation between the following tools catalogues:

- **Available catalogue:** The tools available in the company
- **Company catalogue:** Tools developed in the company or tools needed that aren't in the RTP catalogue, the System Architect can add, remove or edit the tools of this catalogue.
- **RTP catalogue:** reference technology platform (RTP) catalogue, is not possible to add, remove or edit tools of this catalogue.

Figure 2-103: Tool Catalogues.

Within each catalogue, tools are grouped by vendor. When clicking on a tool all its information is loaded into right side (Figure 2-103 B), the basic information of the selected tool is always present:

- **Name**
- **Version**
- **Vendor.** To change the tool vendor click on the "Select" button (Figure 2-103 C), then a tool selection dialog will appear (Figure 2-104).

Vendor Selection ✖

Company Vendor Catalogue:

Name	Url
ITI	https://www.iti.es

RTP Vendor Catalogue:

Name	Url
ACME	http://www.ACME.com/
Wayne Enterprises	http://www.waynee.com/
Stark Industries	http://www.starki.com/
Lex Corporation	http://www.lexcorporation.com

Figure 2-104: Vendor selection.

- **Description**
- **Deployment.** The deployment (Figure 2-103 **D**) of a tool can be:
 - Server
 - Workstation (or PC)

The remaining information of the tool is organized in tabs:

- **Licenses** (Figure 2-103 **E**)
- **ETFs** (Figure 2-103 **F**)
- **Extensions** (Figure 2-103 **G**)
- **IT Requirements** (Figure 2-103 **H**)

2.6.4.1 Licenses

The **Licenses** tab (Figure 2-105) allows indicating if the tool is open-source, managing the tool licenses and adding or removing the selected tool from the **Available Tool Catalogue**.

Figure 2-105: Licenses

The licenses tab is composed of the following fields:

- **Open-source** (Figure 2-105 **A**). If the tool is distributed as open-source the button should be checked.
- **Licenses** (Figure 2-105 **B**). A table with the licenses with which the tool is distributed is shown. Licenses can be added or removed, when a new license is added the dialog **Add new license** (Figure 2-106) opens. In this dialog you can edit the following fields:
 - **Type**. The license can be of type (Figure 2-106 **A**):
 - **Free**
 - **Locked**. For a single user
 - **Floating**. Different users at the same time but the number of users is fixed
 - **Dongle**. Use the tool on any computer
 - **Description** (Figure 2-106 **B**)
 - **URL** (Figure 2-106 **C**)
 - **Maximum users** (Figure 2-106 **D**). Maximum number of users supported by the license.
 - **Maximum computers** (Figure 2-106 **E**). Maximum number of computers supported by the license.
 - **Duration** (Figure 2-106 **F**). It can be:
 - **Permanent**
 - **Period**

- **Minimum duration** in case of **Period** (Figure 2-106 **G**)
- **Maximum duration** in case of **Period** (Figure 2-106 **H**)

Add new license

A Type: Free

B Description: lus id vidit volumus mandamus, vide veritus democritum te nec, ei eos debet libris consulatu. No mei ferri graeco dicunt, ad cum veri accommodare. Sed at malis omnesque delicata, usu et iusto zzril meliore. Dicunt maiorum eloquentiam cum cu, sit summo dolor essent te. Ne quodsi nusquam legendos has, ea dicit voluptua eloquentiam pro, ad sit quas qualisque. Eos vocibus deserunt quaestio ei.

C URL: http://www.iti.es/Loremlpsum

D Max users: 0

E Max computers: 0

F Duration: Permanent

G Min duration: 0 months

H Max duration: 0 months

OK Cancel

Figure 2-106: Add new license.

The System Architect can also add or remove licenses of this tool in the Available Tool Catalogue. When a tool is acquired by the company should be added to the Available Tool Catalogue. When, for example, a license expires this tool should be eliminated from the catalogue.

Selecting a license and clicking in the **Add to Available Catalogue** button (Figure 2-105 **C**) the tool is added with the selected license. To remove a license from the Available Tool Catalogue just select the license and click on the **Remove from Available Catalogue** button Figure 2-105 **D**).

2.6.4.2 ETFs.

ETFs tab (Figure 2-107) Engineering Tool Functions that the tool provides. ETFs tab allows the System Architect to manage Engineering Tool Functions that the tool provides.

As mentioned at the beginning ETFs can be internal to the tool or IOS related (for interoperability purposes). All of them are organized per Engineering Domain. But in the case of IOS ETFs, it has to be differentiated between vertical and cross domain. Cross engineering domains can only be used linked to another (vertical) domain. For example Tracked Resource Set or Configuration Management ETFs can only be used if they are linked to a vertical domain like Requirement Management or Quality Management. For this reason the

ETFs are organized in two types, Vertical and Cross, and the ETFs editor has two tabs, **Vertical** ETFs (Figure 2-107 A) and **Cross** ETFs (Figure 2-107 B).

Figure 2-107: Vertical ETFs

Both **Vertical** and **Cross** ETFs can be filtered by Engineering Domain (Figure 2-107 C).

2.6.4.2.1 Vertical ETFs

The System Architect can open the **Add Vertical ETFs** dialog clicking in the **Add** button (Figure 2-108 D), then just select the desired ETFs in the ETFs table and add them clicking the **OK** button (Figure 2-108 C). ETFs can be filtered by Engineering Domain (Figure 2-108 A).

Figure 2-108: Add Vertical ETFs.

2.6.4.2.2 Cross ETFs

In the same way Cross ETFs can be added to the selected tool clicking the **Add** button in the **Cross** tab, then the **Add Cross ETFs** dialog is shown. The System Architect can select the vertical Target Engineering Domain (Figure 2-109 **A**) and filter by Cross Engineering Domain (Figure 2-109 **B**), finally select the Cross ETFs (Figure 2-109 **C**) which will be added and click the **OK** button (Figure 2-109 **D**).

Figure 2-109: Add Cross ETFs

2.6.4.3 Tool Extensions

The System Architect can indicate the tools that extend or the tools that are extended by the selected tool.

Figure 2-110: Tool Extensions

- **Extended by.** To add tools that extend the selected tool click on the **Add** button (Figure 2-110 **A**), then a tool selection dialog opens (Figure 2-111). In the dialog you can search for the desired tool writing the name or the vendor in the text box (Figure 2-111 **A**), then select the tools you want to add (Figure 2-111 **B**). To remove a tool just select it and click on the **Remove** button (Figure 2-110 **C**).

Figure 2-111: Add Extended By Tools.

- Extends.** To add tools that are extended by the tool being edited click on the **Add** button (Figure 2-110 **B**), then a tool selection dialog opens (it is like Figure 2-111). In the dialog a search for the desired tool can be done writing the name or the vendor in the text box (Figure 2-111 **A**). Then select the tools to be added (Figure 2-111 **B**). To remove a tool just select it a click on the **Remove** button (Figure 2-110 **D**).

2.6.4.4 Tool IT Requirements

The IT Requirements tab (Figure 2-112) is divided into two trees. In the top of the tab there is a tree with the **System Requirements** (Figure 2-112 **A**) and the **Network Requirements** (Figure 2-112 **B**), in the bottom there is a tree for **Resident Software** (Figure 2-112 **C**) and **Remote Software** (Figure 2-112 **D**) needed by the tool.

Figure 2-112: Tool IT Requirements.

System Requirements can be added, deleted and edited (Figure 2-113).

Figure 2-113: System Requirements menu.

To add a new system requirement click the mouse right button on the **System Requirements** item of the tree and select the **Add System Requirements** menu item. Then a **System Requirements** dialog will appear (Figure 2-114). The fields of system requirements that can be introduced are:

- **Operating system family** (Figure 2-114 **A**). E.g. Windows, Linux, etc.
- **Operating system version** (Figure 2-114 **B**). E.g. 8.1, 10, Ubuntu 15.10, etc.
- **Minimum RAM** (Figure 2-114 **C**)

- **Minimum HDD** (Figure 2-114 **D**)
- **Architecture** (Figure 2-114 **E**)
- **Processors** (Figure 2-114 **F**). A list of processors identified by:
 - **Family**. E.g. Intel, AMD, etc.
 - **Version**. E.g. Core i5-6600K, Athlon II X4 750k, etc.

To add a new processor select a processor **Family** (Figure 2-114 **G**), select a processor **Version** (Figure 2-114 **H**), then click the **Add** button (Figure 2-114 **I**). These fields are also editable.

To remove a processor just select it and click on the **Remove** button (Figure 2-114 **J**).

Add System Requirements

A Family: Linux

B Version: ubuntu 15.10

C Min RAM: 2 GB

D Min HDD: 1 GB

E Architecture: 64 bits

F Processors

Family: Intel **G** Version: Core i5-6600K **H** **I** Add

Family	Version
Intel	Core i5-6600K
AMD	Athlon II X4 750k

J Remove

OK Cancel

Figure 2-114: Add System Requirements dialog.

To edit or remove a system requirement mouse right click on it and select the corresponding menu item (Figure 2-113), **Edit System Requirements** or **Remove System Requirements**. In case of edition a dialog **Edit System Requirements**, similar to **Add System Requirements** (Figure 2-114), will appear, and it works in the same way.

Figure 2-115: Network Requirements menu.

To edit the minimum bandwidth required click the mouse right button on the **Bandwidth** item of the tree and select the **Edit Bandwidth** menu item (Figure 2-115), then a little dialog to edit it appears (Figure 2-116).

Figure 2-116: Minimum Bandwidth.

The tree at the bottom as already said contains the software requirements: Resident Software and Remote Software. It works in the same way for both and the software can be tools or services.

Tools can be added through the item menu **Add Tools** (Figure 2-117 **B**). Once clicked a dialog to **Select Tools** is opened. It works like the previous dialogues to add tools, with a text box to search tools and a list of tools to add (Figure 2-111). Tools can be removed by, selecting it then selecting the **Remove Tool** menu item (Figure 2-117 **B**).

Figure 2-117: Resident and Remote Software menu.

Services can be added by the item menu **Add Service** (Figure 2-117 **E**). Then the **Add Service** dialog appears, and the name of the service can be written in the text box (Figure 2-118). In order to remove a service, just select it and click on the **Remove Service** menu item (Figure 2-117 **E**). These services can be also edited by clicking on each one of them and selecting **Edit Service** menu item (Figure 2-117 **E**), then a dialog like the **Add Service** opens.

Figure 2-118: Add Service dialog.

The system also allows specifying different requirement alternatives. For doing so, the menu item **Add Alternatives** (Figure 2-117 **C**) has to be selected. It allows adding **Options** (Figure 2-117 **D**) to the alternatives. Within each option, either tools or services can be added as seen above.

2.6.5 Vendor Catalogues Edition

Vendor Catalogues is a simple editor where the tool vendors are shown and edited. The editor is structured in two different sections: **Company vendors** (Figure 2-119 **A**) in the top and **RTP vendors** (Figure 2-119 **B**) in the bottom. From both only the Company Vendor Catalogue can be modified (add, edit tools).

In order to edit a vendor, just select it and click on the **Edit** button. The **Edit Vendor** dialog will appear (Figure 2-120). The fields to edit are just:

- **Name**
- **Description**
- **URL**

Figure 2-119: Vendor Catalogues.

To add a new vendor click on the **Add** button, a very similar dialog to **Edit Vendor** dialog will appear. Select a vendor and click on the **Remove** button to remove it.

Edit Vendor

Name: ITI

Desc: ITI is a Reference Technological Centre specialized in Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) Research, Development and Innovation, offering to the computer industry the possibility of adding new technologies and capabilities developed in R&D&I projects to their products, processes or businesses. It was established in 1994 by a joint initiative of the Polytechnic University of Valencia (UPV), the Institute of Small and Medium Enterprises of Valencia (IMPIVA), and a group of companies in the information technology sector. It has a

URL: <http://www.iti.es/>

OK Cancel

Figure 2-120: Edit Vendor.

2.6.6 Company IT Infrastructure Edition

This section specifies how to use the editor for editing the Company IT Infrastructure in order to use it later when validating the SEE for checking that the SEE IT infrastructure is supported by the Company IT Infrastructure.

The available company IT infrastructure is organized in three main tabs:

- **Machines**
- **Services**
- **Networks**

2.6.6.1 Machines

A table with the list of machines available in the company is shown (Figure 2-121), the characteristics of a machine are:

- **Name**
- **Type. Workstation or Server**
- **Operating System family**
- **Operating System version**
- **Processor family**
- **Processor version**
- **Architecture. X64 or X86**
- **RAM (GB)**
- **HDD (GB)**

Figure 2-121: Machines.

To add a new machine click on the **Add** button (Figure 2-121 **A**) and a new machine is created in the table. For removing a machine select it by clicking on the row, then select on the **Remove** button (Figure 2-121 **B**). The items of the table can be edited just clicking on the cell and writing the new value (Figure 2-122). In the case of type of deployment or architecture a drop down list (Figure 2-123) is shown with the selectable values.

Figure 2-122: Field edition.

Name	Type	OS family	OS version
pc-3	Workstation	Windows	8.1
pc-4	Server	Linux	Ubuntu 10.04
pc-5	Workstation	Windows	7
pc-6	Workstation	Windows	7
pc-10	Workstation	Linux	Ubuntu 14.04

Figure 2-123: Type selection.

2.6.6.2 Services

To describe a Service in the IT infrastructure three fields are used:

- **Type.** It's a free text field where define the type of the service (database, web server, etc.)
- **Name.** Free text field where edit the service name
- **Description.** Brief description of the service, it's a free text field too

To add a new service click on the **Add** button (Figure 2-124 **A**) and a new service is created.

To remove a previously created service select it by clicking on the row, then click on the **Remove** button (Figure 2-124 **B**).

Services can be edited just clicking on the cell and writing the new value (Figure 2-124 **C**),

Figure 2-124: Services.

2.6.6.3 Networks

Networks tab is divided in two zones: one at the top with the list of networks available in the company, and at the bottom a pane with the information of the selected network.

The list of networks available in the company contains the following fields:

- **Name**
- **Description**

Moreover, this table allows to add new networks clicking on the **Add** button (Figure 2-125 **A**). For removing a network just select it by clicking on the row, then press on the **Remove** button (Figure 2-125 **B**).

Networks name can be edited just clicking on the cell and writing the new value (Figure 2-125 **C**),

Figure 2-125: Network machines.

In the bottom more information about the selected network is shown (Figure 2-125 **D**), machines that are in the network (**Machines** tab), services in the network (**Services** tab) and other networks connected (**Networks** tab) to this one.

In the machines tab are shown the machines connected to the network in the **Selected Machines** table, at right. The machines not connected are listed at the left, in the **Available Machines** table.

To connect a machine to the network, select it in the **Available Machines** table, then click on the > button (Figure 2-125 **E**). To disconnect it just select it in the **Selected Machines** table, then click on the < button (Figure 2-125 **F**).

The **Services** tab works like the **Machines** tab, services in the network are shown in the **Selected services** table. At right, services not provided are listed at the left, in the **Available services** table.

To add a service to the network select it in the **Available services** table, then click on the > button (Figure 2-126 **A**). To remove it just select it in the **Selected services** table, then click on the < button" (Figure 2-126 **B**).

Figure 2-126: Network services.

As before the **Networks** tab works like the **Machines** tab, networks connected to this network are shown in the **Selected networks** table at right. Networks not connected are listed at the left, in the **Available networks** table.

To connect a network select it in the **Available networks** table, then click on the **>** button (Figure 2-127 **A**). To disconnect it just select it in the **Selected networks** table, then click on the **<** button" (Figure 2-127 **B**).

Figure 2-127: Network connections.

3 Developer environment

To develop with the EPF-Composer 1.5.1.5 plugins and the Eclipse development environment follow the next steps:

1. Install Java SE Development Kit 6u45:
2. Download and extract eclipse 3.6.2 32 bits
3. Download and extract in eclipse:
 - Delta pack 3.6.2
 - EMF 2.6.1
 - GEF 3.6.2
 - EMFT Transaction 1.4.0
 - EMFT Validation 1.4.0
 - UML2 3.1.2
 - EMF Query 1.4.0
 - GMF 2.4.0
 - OCL 1.3.0
4. Install EGit in eclipse:
 - **Help**→**Install New Software**
 - **Add Repository** <http://download.eclipse.org/egit/updates-2.1>
 - Select **Eclipse EGit**
 - Select **Next->...**
5. Import EPF Composer:
 - **File**->**Import**
 - Select **Git->Projects** from Git URI:
[git://git.eclipse.org/gitroot/epf/org.eclipse.epf.composer.git](http://git.eclipse.org/gitroot/epf/org.eclipse.epf.composer.git)
 - Select only **EPF_1515**
 - **Import Existing Projects**
6. Run EPF Composer:
 - Open **org.eclipse.epf.rcp.ui** → **composer_win32.product**
 - Select **Overview** tab
 - **Synchronize**
 - **Launch an Eclipse application** (an error message appears)
 - **Close** error window
 - **Run** → **Run Configurations...**
 - Select **composer product**
 - **Main** tab:
 - **Check Java Runtime Environment jre6**
 - Plug-ins tab:
 - Select **Launch with: all workspace and enabled target plug-ins**
 - **Run** (The EPF-Composer application should start running)

4 Installation guide

Those are the instructions for installing the PB. After following these instructions you will have:

- An EPF Composer instance with the required plugins providing Platform Builder features
- A library with a sample of a tailored process
- Tool, vendor and ETF catalogues available for configuration

The last release of the Platform Builder plugins, catalogues and documentation can be found in [Zenodo](#).

Installation and configuration steps:

1. Download and install EPF Composer 1.5.1.5: (You can avoid this step if you have already installed it): http://www.eclipse.org/epf/downloads/tool/epf1.5.0_downloads.php
2. Copy the jar files contained in the *pb-plugins* folder in the *plugins* folder of the **EPF-Composer 1.5.1.5** that you have installed in the previous step. **Do this when the EPF-Composer is not running, contrarily you won't be able to access the new functionality until you restart EPF.**
3. Run (start) the **EPF Composer 1.5.1.5** that you have installed.
4. Select Authoring perspective if it is not already selected.
5. Create a new library "*File* → *New* → *Method Library*".
6. Import the EPF Composer *plug-in* included in the *pb-mcp* folder "*File* → *Import* → *Method Plug-ins* → *Next* → *Browse* → ... → *Next* → *Select All* → *Finish*"
7. Open the Configuring perspective "*Window* → *Open Perspective* → *Other...* → *Configuring* → *OK*"
8. Open the Platform Builder Settings editor "*Platform Builder* -> *Platform Builder Settings*".
9. In the *Catalogues* tab browse for the RTP Tool Catalogue (*rtp-tool-catalogue.xml*), the *RTP Vendor Catalogue* (*rtp-vendor-catalogue.xml*) and the *ETF Official Catalogue* (*etf-official-catalogue.xml*) and update them. (This step is now manual in the future these catalogues will be automatically imported).
10. Close the *Platform Builder Settings* editor and return to the *Authoring perspective*.

Now you have the Platform Builder ready to be used for tailoring processes and generating SEE.

5 Terms, Abbreviations and Definitions

Please add additional terms, abbreviations and definitions for your deliverable.

CRYSTAL	CR itical SYST em Engineering AcceL eration
R	Report
P	Prototype
D	Demonstrator
O	Other
PU	Public
PP	Restricted to other program participants (including the JU).
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the JU).
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the JU).
WP	Work Package
SP	Subproject
PB	Platform Builder
SEE	System Engineering Environment
ETF	Engineering Tool Function
EM	Engineering Method
PB-MCP	Platform Builder Method Content Plug-in
IOS	Interoperability Specification
RTP	Reference Technology Platform
EPF	Eclipse Process Framework
UMA	Unified Method Architecture
IT	Information Technology

Table 5-1: Terms, Abbreviations and Definitions

6 References

[D602.012, 2015]	CRYSTAL project. Meta-model specification – V2, 2015
[D602.021, 2014]	CRYSTAL project, Platform Builder Specification - V1, 2014
[EPF-1.5]	Eclipse Process Framework-1.5, available at: http://www.eclipse.org/epf/downloads/tool/epf1.5.0_downloads.php
[SPEM, 2008]	OMG, Software & System Process Engineering Metamodel Specification , 2008

7 Annex

7.1 Annex I: Catalogues

This section provides information about the different catalogues needed through the Platform Builder process. The list of catalogues is the following:

- EM Catalogue
- ETF Catalogue
- Tool Catalogue

The following sections provide an overview of each one of them.

7.1.1 EM Catalogue

As explained in the Tailoring phase, the catalogue of EMs (Engineering Method) is built using Task elements of EPF inside a Method Content Plug-in of EPF Composer (the PB-MCP) and categorized under the EM Discipline. The following table shows the EM information:

Field	Description	Type	Mandatory
Identifier	Identifier of the EM. Unique.	Alphanumeric	Yes
Name	Name of the EM identifier.	Free text	Yes
Description	Description of the EM	Free text	No
Roles	Roles that can perform this EM	List of roles in the EPF library.	No
Artifacts	Artifacts used in this EM.	List of work products in the EPF library.	No

Table 7-1: EM fields' information

7.1.2 ETF Catalogue

This is a catalogue of Engineering Tool Functions that is used for two different purposes:

- It is used by Tool Vendors when creating the Tool Descriptor of a given Tool in order to identify the ETF this tool supports.
- It is used in the Configuration phase of the Platform Builder Workflow in order to identify which ETF will be used in each EM of the List of EM of the process.

The catalogue contains a list of Engineering Domains.

Field	Description	Type	Mandatory
Id	Unique identifier for the	Alphanumeric	Yes

	Engineering Domain.		
Name	Name of the Engineering Domain.	Free text	Yes
Type	Type of the Engineering Domain, Vertical or Cross.	Type enumeration	

The information to be contained in the catalogue of ETFs for defining them is listed in this table.

Field	Description	Type	Mandatory
Id	Unique identifier for the ETF.	Alphanumeric	Yes
Name	Name of the ETF. Used for listing purposes.	Free text	Yes
Type	This field states if this ETF is an IOS service or an internal function tool.	Type enumeration	Yes
IOS-operation	In case of IOS operations this is used to imply the type of operation: Read, Create, Update, Delete	IOS-operation-enumeration	Yes (for IOS)
Description	Short description about the feature provided by this ETF.	Free text	No
Version	This field pretends to support defining and distinguishing between different versions of the same ETF.		Yes
IOS-spec	In case of IOS this field should identify the specification to which this ETF belongs.	IOS-spec-enumeration	Yes (for IOS)
Engineering-domain	The identifier of the engineering domain to which this ETF belongs.	Engineering-domain-enumeration	Yes
Tool-class	Tools that can provide this ETF. (Under evaluation for V2)	Tool-class-enumeration	Yes
Artifacts	Artifacts used by this ETF.	Artifact elements.	No

Table 7-2: ETF information in the ETF catalogue

Each Artifact element is detailed with the following information:

Field	Description	Type	Mandatory
Id	Unique identifier for the Artifact.	Alphanumeric	Yes
Name	Name of the Artifact. Used for listing purposes.	Free text	Yes
Mode	This field states if this artifact is used as input or output.	Mode-enumeration	Yes

	(Under evaluation from V2)		
Description	Short description about this artifact.	Free text	No
Format-code	Specification of the format of this artifact.	URI or free text.	Yes

Table 7-3: Artifacts information in the ETF catalogue

Moreover, this catalogue also provides information about IOS pairs of ETF. This information is used for establishing the valid pairs of ETF consumer and ETF provider.

Field	Description	Type	Mandatory
Pair-node-consumer	The identifier of the ETF working as consumer.	Alphanumeric	Yes
Pair-node-provider	The identifier of the ETF working as provider.	Alphanumeric	Yes

Table 7-4: ETF pairs of the kind consumer-provider

Enumerations: most of them are currently built and their possible values will vary depending on the new IOS specifications identified and defined in CRYSTAL.

- Type-enumeration: {IOS/TOOL}
- IOS-operation-enumeration: {Create, Read, Update, Delete}
- IOS-spec-enumeration: {http://open-services.net/ns/rm#, http://open-services.net/ns/am#,...}
- Engineering-domain-enumeration: {Requirement Management, Architecture Management, PLC Management, Quality Management, Simulation Management,...}
- Tool-class-enumeration: {Any, Requirement Management, Architecture Management, PLC Management, Quality Management,...}
- Mode-enumeration: {input, output}

7.1.2.1 Example

This is an example of an Engineering Tool Function in the ETF catalogue which includes artifacts:


```

<ef ef-id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_CON_GET_REQ">
  <ef-name>Consume Requirement List - OSLC 2.0</ef-name>
  <ef-type>IOS</ef-type>
  <ef-ios-operation>Read</ef-ios-operation>
  <ef-description>Obtain a list of requirements based on the OSLC specification based on a search criteria.
  <ef-version>0.1</ef-version>
  <ef-ios-spec>http://open-services.net/ns/rm#</ef-ios-spec>
  <ef-engineering-domain>Requirement Management</ef-engineering-domain>
  <ef-tool-class>Any</ef-tool-class>
  <ef-artifacts>
    <ef-artifact ef-artifact-id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_Requirement" ef-artifact-mode="output">
      <ef-artifact-name>Requirement</ef-artifact-name>
      <ef-artifact-description>List of requirements satisfying the search criteria.
      <ef-artifact-format-code>http://open-services.net/ns/rm#Requirement</ef-artifact-format-code>
    </ef-artifact>
  </ef-artifacts>
</ef>

```

Figure 7-1: ETF definition example in the ETF catalogue.

Example of a pair consumer-provider:

```

<ef-pairs>
  <!-- Requirement Management -->
  <ef-pair>
    <ef-pair-node-consumer>IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_CON_GET_REQ</ef-pair-node-consumer>
    <ef-pair-node-provider>IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_PRO_GET_REQ</ef-pair-node-provider>
  </ef-pair>
  <ef-pair>
    <ef-pair-node-consumer>IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_CON_UPD_REQ</ef-pair-node-consumer>
    <ef-pair-node-provider>IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_PRO_UPD_REQ</ef-pair-node-provider>
  </ef-pair>
</ef-pairs>

```

Figure 7-2: ETF example pair.

7.1.3 Tool Catalogue

A tool catalogue is composed by a set of Tool Descriptors (Annex II: Descriptors).

7.2 Annex II: Descriptors

This Annex is used for detailing descriptors being used in the Platform Builder. The currently envisaged descriptors are:

- Tool descriptor;
- IT infrastructure descriptor.

The next subsections provide information about each one of them.

7.2.1 Tool Descriptor

This descriptor is used for defining each tool in terms of:

- ETF(s) provided by this tool;
- If this tool extends or is extended by any other tool;
- The IT requirements required for using it.

The tool vendor defines the tool descriptor for the tools it sells or provides. The necessary information for these descriptors is:

Field	Description	Type	Mandatory
Id	Unique identifier for the tool.	Alphanumeric	Yes
Name	Name of the Tool. Used for listing purposes.	Free text	Yes
Version	This field pretends to support defining and distinguishing between different versions of the same Tool.	Alphanumeric	Yes
Vendor	Identifier of the Vendor.	Alphanumeric	Yes
Description	Short description about the feature provided by this ETF.	Free text	No
Type	Engineering domain. (Under evaluation for V2)	Engineering-domain- enumeration (see ETF catalogue)	No
Extended-by	This field is used when the vendor of a tool knows that this tool is extended by another. Used for stating the use of IOS adapters.	Identifier of the tool extending this tool. Several.	No
Extends	This field is used when the vendor of a tool knows that this tool extends the features of other tools. Used for stating the use of IOS adapters.	Identifier of the tool extended by this tool. Several.	No

SW-function	ETF provided by this tool.	ETF valid identifier. Several. The SW-function element can contain Artifact elements for defining if needed the proprietary artifacts.	Yes
Cross-SW-function	Cross ETF provided by this tool, with the target Engineering Domain.	ETF valid identifier. Several. The Cross-SW-function should contain at least one target Engineering Domain	No
IT-requirement	Specifies the IT requirements of the tool. (Under evaluation for V2)	IT requirement element.	Yes

Table 7-5: Tool descriptor information

IT requirements and Artifact elements are currently defined, as showed in the following tables, but not implemented in the current version of this deliverable. They might be changed in version V2 of the prototype.

An IT requirement element is defined as follows:

Field	Description	Type	Mandatory
Network-deployment	Network required information	Network-deployment element	Yes
OS	The OS	OS-enumeration	Yes
Resident SW	SW (tools) that should be installed in the same machine.	Identifier of a tool. Several.	Yes
Remote SW	SW (tools) that should be installed in external machines.	Identifier of a tool. Several.	Yes

Table 7-6: IT requirement element for tools

The artifact element is used if the tool vendor wants to specify artifacts in regard to the ones defined in the ETF catalogue:

- Extensions for IOS standard artifacts, used in ETF of type IOS.
- Artifacts used in ETF of type Tool.

Each Artifact element is detailed with the following information:

Field	Description	Type	Mandatory
Id	Unique identifier for the Artifact.	Alphanumeric	Yes
Name	Name of the Artifact. Used for listing purposes.	Free text	Yes
Mode	This field states if this artifact is used as input or output. (Under evaluation for V2)	Mode- enumeration	Yes
Description	Short description of this artifact.	Free text	No
Format-code	Specification of the format of this artifact.	URI or free text.	Yes

Table 7-7: Artifacts element for tools

7.2.1.1 Example

This is an example of a tool descriptor.

```

<tool-catalogue timestamp="0">
  <sw-component-descriptor id="_pJJRcI_nFeiObsERx5XzNw" name="New Tool" version="0.0.1" vendor="_Z9Y48I_nFeiObsERx5XzNw" open-source="true"
  deployment="Workstation">
    <description>
      Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam,
      quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum
      dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.
    </description>
    <type/>
    <licenses>
      <license id="_HFIVYI_nFeiObsERx5XzNw" type="free" desc="Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut
      labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute
      irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in
      culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum." url="http://www.iti.loren.ipsum.com" duration="permanent" max-users="0" max-computers="0" min-
      duration="0" max-duration="0"/>
    </licenses>
    <extended-by sw-component-id="YetAnotherRequirementManagerTool-RM-PRO-Adapter"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_CON_GET_REQ"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_PRO_GET_REQ"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_CON_UPD_REQ"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_PRO_UPD_REQ"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_CON_CRE_REQ"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_PRO_CRE_REQ"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_CON_DEL_REQ"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_PRO_DEL_REQ"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_CON_DUI_PICK_REQ"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_PRO_DUI_PICK_REQ"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_CON_GET_REQCOL"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_PRO_GET_REQCOL"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_CON_UPD_REQCOL"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_PRO_UPD_REQCOL"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_CON_CRE_REQCOL"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_PRO_CRE_REQCOL"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_CON_DEL_REQCOL"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_PRO_DEL_REQCOL"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_CON_DUI_PICK_REQCOL"/>
    <sw-function id="IOS_OSLC_RM_2.0_PRO_DUI_PICK_REQCOL"/>
    <sw-function id="ANALYZE_REQUIREMENT"/>
    <sw-function id="MANAGE_REQUIREMENT"/>
    <sw-function id="FORMALIZE_REQUIREMENT"/>
    <sw-function id="VALIDATE_REQUIREMENT"/>
  </sw-component-descriptor>
  <system-requirements>
    <os id="_Egz7QI_qFeiObsERx5XzNw" family="Linux" version="Ubuntu 16.04" minimum-ram="4" minimum-hdd="2" arch="X64">
      <proc family="Intel" version="Core i5-6600K"/>
      <proc family="AMD" version="Athlon II X4 750K"/>
    </os>
  </system-requirements>
  <resident-sw>
    <sw-id>TEST_GENERATOR_ID</sw-id>
    <service id="_MuLDkI_qFeiObsERx5XzNw" name="MySQL" desc=""/>
  </resident-sw>
  <remote-sw>
    <sw-alternatives>
      <sw-alternative>
        <sw-id>YetAnotherQualityManagerToolAdapter</sw-id>
      </sw-alternative>
      <sw-alternative>
        <sw-id>YetAnotherRequirementManagerTool</sw-id>
      </sw-alternative>
    </sw-alternatives>
  </remote-sw>

```

Figure 7-3: Example of Tool descriptor.

7.2.2 IT Infrastructure Descriptor

This descriptor describes the machines, services and networks available in the company in order to use it for validation purposes.

The list of machines contains:

Field	Description	Type	Mandatory
Id	Unique identifier for the machine.	Alphanumeric	Yes
Name	Name of the Machine.	Free text	Yes
Description	Description of the machine	Free text	No
Type	Deployment of the machine, Server or Workstation.	Deployment enumeration	Yes
OS-family	Operating System family.	Free text	No
OS-version	Operating System version.	Free text	No
Proc-family	Processor family	Free text	No
Proc-version	Processor version	Free text	No
Arch	Architecture, x86 or x64	Architecture enumeration	No
RAM	RAM memory	Integer	Yes
HDD	Hard disk memory	Integer	Yes

Table 7-8: Machines

The list of services contains:

Field	Description	Type	Mandatory
Id	Unique identifier for the service.	Alphanumeric	Yes
Name	Name of the service.	Free text	Yes
Description	Description of the service	Free text	No
Type	Type of the service.	Free text	No

Table 7-9: Services

The list of networks contains:

Field	Description	Type	Mandatory
Id	Unique identifier for the network.	Alphanumeric	Yes
Name	Name of the Network.	Free text	Yes
Description	Description of the Network	Free text	No
Networks	List of Networks connected to the network.	Alphanumeric	No

Services	List of services available in the network.	Alphanumeric	No
Machines	List of the machines connected to the network.	Alphanumeric	No

Table 7-10: Networks